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Interconnected Nord-Est
Innovation Ecosystem

Cross-Cutting Activity #4

Education
& Lifelong Learning

i NEST

Milestone #27

Report

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1. Introduction

The objectives of the cross-cutting action “Education & Lifelong Learning” within the iNEST project and in territorial context of the Ecosystem have been focused on the development of knowledge, skills, attitudes and values that enable people to contribute to and benefit from an inclusive and sustainable future. Such approach is based on two pillars:

- Education, to equip students with the capabilities they need to thrive and become active, responsible and engaged citizens,
- Lifelong Learning, which is strategic to bolster innovation within society, and in particular into SMEs.

The state of the art developed in the frame of Milestone #25 of iNEST project [1] evidenced that the effort of iNEST Partner Universities in education and lifelong learning is strong, highly motivated and with relevant attention to innovation. In that report, some challenges have been identified:

- developing the capability, in perfect agreement with the mission of iNEST Ecosystem, of sharing, improving, upgrading these excellent experiences among universities,
- making such experiences and tools available not only to own students, but also to students still in high schools,
- opening new up-skilling scenarios for those already involved in professional activities and jobs,
- contributing to exploiting of Nord-Est potential by realizing a systemic vision of the overall Education path of persons.

Thus, iNEST is trying to develop, as an ecosystem, an overall and integrated vision of educational path of people, starting from high school and coming up to lifelong learning during professional life (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Overall and integrated vision of Education path of persons

Under these premises, the key-areas identified for action at the ecosystem level are:

- **Guidance, Counselling and Tutoring**
- **Education paths, tools and methodologies**
- **Inter- e trans-disciplinary initiatives**
- **Lifelong learning**

As described in the Report summarizing Milestone #26 [2], iNEST elaborated a comprehensive plan for Education and Lifelong Learning initiatives in the Ecosystem:

- **Guidance, Counselling and Tutoring:** organization of a POT-PLS Forum to share best practices and start the design of drop-out recovering pilot-projects;
- **Education paths, tools and methodologies:** 15 initiatives, pilot-projects, tools and methodologies to support advanced and efficient learning processes, as shown in Fig. 2;
- **Inter- e trans-disciplinary initiatives:** 19 Minors, Challenges and Hackatons addressed to students of iNEST Partner Universities, as shown in Fig. 3;
- **Lifelong learning: 26 Lifelong Learning initiatives,** as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 2 – iNEST Plan about initiatives, pilot-projects, tools and methodologies to support advanced and efficient learning processes

Figure 3 – iNEST Plan about Minors, Challenges and Hackatons

Figure 4 – iNEST Plan about Lifelong Learning initiatives

This Report reviews the actions already performed (Annexes #1, #2 and #3) and those scheduled for the final period of the project (October 2024-December 2025, corresponding to Milestone #28, collected in Annexes #4, #5 and #6).

2. Guidance, Counselling and Tutoring

iNEST Universities are highly involved in PLS and POT initiatives, as reported in Table 1 [3-4], showing the list of approved PLS (National Plan for Science degrees) and POT (Orientation and Tutoring Programmes) programmes running from 2023 to 2025. The yellow background displays projects related to iNEST and its Spokes thematic areas.

Type	Coordinator	Title	U N I T N	U N I U D	I U A V	U N I P D	U N I V E	U N I V R	U N I T S
PLS	UNIBO	Progetto Nazionale Geologia				✓			✓
PLS	UNICT	Progetto Nazionale di Biologia e Biotecnologie	✓	✓				✓	✓
PLS	UNIMI	Progetto Nazionale di INFORMATICA		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
PLS	UNIMIB	Progetto Nazionale Chimica				✓			✓
PLS	UNIMIB	Progetto Nazionale LS di Scienza dei Materiali							✓
PLS	UNIPA	Progetto Nazionale di Statistica				✓			✓
PLS	UNIPA	Progetto Nazionale di FISICA	✓			✓		✓	✓
PLS	UNIPI	Progetto nazionale di Matematica		✓		✓		✓	✓
PLS	UNIVPM	PLS in Scienze Naturali e Ambientali				✓	✓		✓
POT	UNICAMPANIA	PROMETHEUS 2.0				✓		✓	
POT	UNIPI	UniSco - Azioni Università-Scuola per competenze in lingue, letterature, mediazione linguistica				✓			✓
POT	UNIROMA1	MedOdontOrientaDomain-MOOD				✓		✓	✓
POT	IUAV	POT_Architettura		✓	✓				✓
POT	UNIROMA1	SUL - Scuola e Università per Lettere				✓	✓	✓	
POT	UNISALENTO	Scienze delle Attività Motorie e Sportive				✓		✓	
POT	UNINA	INGEGNERIA.POT	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
POT	UNISI	Verso. Sistemi di orientamento e tutorato per le professioni educative e formative		✓		✓		✓	✓
POT	UNISA	Geolocalizzazione Politico-Sociologica per orientarsi nel mondo UNIversitario				✓		✓	✓
POT	UNIMOL	SISSA3EFG - Sistema Integrato Studenti Scienze Agrarie, Alimentari, Animali, Enologiche, Forestali, Gastronomiche		✓		✓		✓	
POT	UNISALENTO	C.A.R.E: Orientamento e formazione professione insegnante		✓		✓		✓	
POT	UNIROMA3	Università, scuole e territorio in rete per il patrimonio culturale materiale e immateriale		✓		✓	✓	✓	
POT	UNIPV	V.A.L.E. - P.L.U.S. (Vocational Academic Law Enhancement - Project Law University Student)	✓			✓		✓	✓
POT	UNIPD	Orientare ed Orientarsi tra le Scienze del Farmaco				✓			✓
POT	UNIMI	Tutorato Orientamento Professioni Sanitarie - TOP		✓		✓		✓	
POT	UNITUS	IN DIALOGO CON IL RESTAURO							
POT	UNINA	ServizioSociale.Pot				✓		✓	✓
POT	UNICAMPANIA	NEED_new empathic educational design							
POT	UNITO	TALENTI - ECONOMIA, MANAGEMENT E TURISMO		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
POT	UNIME	OrientaVET: orientamento-tutorato per lo studente				✓			

Table 1 – Recently (August 2023) approved PLS/POT programmes [10-11]

Furthermore, in the frame of PNRR (section called “Orientamento attivo nella transizione scuola università”/ active guidance in the school to university transition), several initiatives are being planned and some are already ongoing in Italian Universities, such as guidance courses” addressed to students finishing high school.

The goal is to support the young generation of a knowledge-based society by improving knowledge about higher education paths, experiential learning, as well as developing: a scientific approach to learning, the availability of self-evaluation tools, transversal competences and employability skills, knowledge on work environments.

iNEST activities have been mainly addressed to coordination and sharing of initiatives and experiences. This will be done during a specific Forum, which will be carried out in February 2025, aimed at sharing best practices and at comparing pilot projects about tutoring and guidance to convert students' drop-out into a new and successful career

3. Educational paths, tools and methodologies

The iNEST Education – State of the Art document [1] evidenced the activities performed by Nord-Est Universities to develop innovative pedagogies, tools and methodologies for innovative and efficient learning processes.

Annex 1 collects the activities performed in the frame of Milestone #27 (October 2023 – September 2024) by iNEST's education partners addressed at developing initiatives, pilot-projects, tools and methodologies to support advanced and efficient learning processes.

9 events have been organized and carried out, with more than 250 participants.

Annex 4 collects the activities, in the same area, scheduled in the frame of Milestone #28 (October 2024 – December 2025).

12 events are being organized.

4. Inter- e trans-disciplinary initiatives

The need of inter- and trans-disciplinary activities has been already intercepted by iNEST Universities, as highlighted in the Education Working Group report published in March 2023 [1]. Furthermore, iNEST Project implemented the opportunity of sharing, coordinating and improving inter-disciplinary approaches, leading learners to an improved vision and attitude to problem solving and a sensibility towards interdisciplinary and lifelong learning.

Annex 2 to this document collects the events performed during Milestone #27 (October 2023 – September 2024), in terms of **Minors subjects, Challenges and Hackathons**.

9 events have been organized and carried out, with more than 250 participants.

Annex 5 collects the activities, in the same area, scheduled in the frame of Milestone #28 (October 2024 – December 2025).

14 events are being organized.

The initiative **Erasmus iNEST**, to be integrated in the recently approved "Italian Erasmus" project (published on the Gazzetta Ufficiale, 27/07/2023), aimed at improving students' mobility between Italian universities, and consequently to further support the genesis of multi- and inter-disciplinary professional profiles, is still under study.

5. Lifelong learning

The Lifelong Learning programme, fully coherent with the framework of iNEST, have been activated, taking into account

- Training programmes aligned with the main topics characterizing each Spoke,
- Structure of courses based on flexibility and blended approaches, with on-line synchronous and a-synchronous MOOCs integrated with meetings with the board of teachers,
- Involvement of teachers and trainers with different backgrounds, both in terms of technical profiles and of professional experience (companies, universities, consultancy services) ,
- Development of a self-developed certification system, based on micro-credential approach.

Annex 3 collects the Lifelong Learning activities performed in the frame of Milestone #27 (October 2023 – September 2024) by iNEST's education partners, according to the above-defined strategy.

5 events have been organized and carried out, with more than 220 participants.

Annex 6 collects the activities, in the same area, scheduled in the frame of Milestone #28 (October 2024 – December 2025).

23 events are being organized.

6. Status of iNEST Plan for Education and Lifelong Learning

At the end of Milestone #27, the status of implementation of iNEST Plan for Education and Lifelong Learning is substantially aligned with the planning defined in Milestone #26.

- ⇒ **23 events, in the different areas individuated, have been performed, with more than 700 participants.**
- ⇒ **49 events, in the different areas individuated, are being organized and will be carried out in the frame of Milestone #28, from October 2024 to December 2025.**

Deviations from the planning are limited to small changes in contents of events or to the replacement of few initiatives.

Milestone #28 will see the fulfilment of all activities designed by the Education Working Group of iNEST.

References

- 1) Education & Lifelong Learning – State of the Art, iNEST – Milestone #25 Report, 2023
- 2) iNEST – Milestone #26 Report, 2024
- 3) MUR, Decreto del Segretario Generale n. 1295, Piano Lauree Scientifiche 2021-2023, 04-08-2023
- 4) MUR, Decreto del Segretario Generale n. 1327, Piani per l'Orientamento e il Tutorato 2021 – 2023, 10-08-2023

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Annex 1

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects Catalogue

***Performed
in the frame of
Milestone #27***

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #1	
Reference Persons	Morselli Daniele & Guido Orzes
Key-descriptors	
Title	Experimental procedure to certify transversal skills to facilitate the transition university to work
TAGS	#Innovative Education #Engineering #Learning Factories
Date	1 test during a challenge-based learning programme that took place from 26 th February to 1 st March
Participants	//
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>This project sought to measure and certify the students' entrepreneurship competence as key competence to favor the transition from university to work. From 26 February to 1 March 2024 25 students coming from all faculties at the Free University of Bolzano participated to the Student Sprint event at the NOI Tech Park of Bolzano (the event was organized outside iNEST but used as a test for the experimental procedure to certify competences). This Challenge Based Learning event was based on Google Design Sprint. Students were given an important challenge by a South Tirolean company, they worked in group and were coached by experts. They found a solution to the challenge and presented it the last day to the companies. Out of the 25 students participating in the Company Sprint Event, 18 gave consent to participate in the experimental procedure to certify the entrepreneurship related competences they had developed during the week. This procedure was made by:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) an online survey to be filled out by the students before the beginning of the event. This survey inquired both qualitatively and quantitatively on how students mastered certain competencies, and in what contexts they had developed them. 2) observations from the coaches. We designed a grid where the coaches could assess the students' performance: write annotations, assess their performance on selected EQF levels. 3) A online survey to be filled out after the challenge were students had to reflect on their competence development and in which future situations they thought they could display this competence. Like in 1 this survey was both qualitative and quantitative. <p>The competence selected for this experimental procedure were based on the EntreComp framework. Based on previous literature, we selected six specific entrepreneurship related sub competencies such as: the ability to tolerate ambiguity and stress, the capacity to apply new tools, the ability to work in heterogeneous groups, the capacity to present an innovative idea. Beside the European Framework EntreComp, we also used the European Qualification Framework to find levels of competence development appropriate for master and bachelor students. At the end of the event, we triangulated data from 1, 2 and 3 to provide students with a certificate. Results suggest that the student's self-perception do not correlate significantly with the coaches' observation. Hence, the observations of the coaches are key for the certification process.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	This experimental procedure will be shared with the iNEST partner and the larger scientific community and be further refined in the Milestone #28.
Website/link	
Notes	
	Picture 1 displays a certificate provided to students that took place to the experimental procedure. The first column relates to the selected competences – we preferred to name them “learning outcomes” as these cannot be automatically translated to other contexts. Based on the selected word (i.e., “learning outcomes”), the readers of the certificate should

be cautious to think that a competence developed in one context (such as the context of the Sprint) can be immediately applied to another context. The second column displays the EQF framework; this makes the outcomes easily comparable to European standards of qualifications. The third column represents the European ESCO framework for transversal competences.

Bolzano, 16 April 2024

To whom it may concern:

participated in the Students Sprint 2024 edition taking place from 26th February to 2nd March at the NOI Tech Park of Bolzano (Italy). This is an intensive five-days experience based on Design Sprint methodology where students are given a company challenge, work in groups to find a creative solution and eventually pitch it to the company.

The following table is the result of an experimental project on competence assessment financed within the PNRR - JNEST (Interconnected Nord-Est Innovation Ecosystem) project. Based on coaches' observations and students' self-reflections, the grid displays the learning outcomes developed during the Student Sprint. The level attained is based on the European Qualification Framework.

Learning outcome	Level of the European Qualification Framework	Transversal skills according to ESCO framework
Work with people of different backgrounds	5	S1.1 - negotiating
Apply new tools and methods	5	S1.2 - liaising and networking
Manage time effectively	4	S1.4 - presenting information
Stay focused and don't give up	6	S1.7 - interviewing & engaging with others to identify needs
Present and communicate effectively an innovative idea or concept	4	S1.8 - working with others
Design a new product/service that has potential end-users/clients	5	S1.9 - solving problems
	https://europa.eu/europass/en/description-eight-efq-levels	https://ec.europa.eu/esco/portal/browse

The EQF levels

3= A range of cognitive and practical skills required to accomplish tasks and solve problems by selecting and applying basic methods, tools, materials and information.

4= A range of cognitive and practical skills required to generate solutions to specific problems in a field of work or study.

5= A comprehensive range of cognitive and practical skills required to develop creative solutions to abstract problems.

6= Advanced skills, demonstrating mastery and innovation, required to solve complex and unpredictable problems in a specialised field of work or study.

7= Specialised problem-solving skills required in research and/or innovation to develop new knowledge and procedures and to integrate knowledge from different fields.

Yours sincerely,

Morselli Daniele, Faculty of Education, Free University of Bolzano

Guido Orzes, Faculty of Engineering, Free University of Bolzano

Alessandro Narduzzo, Faculty of Economics, Free University of Bolzano

Daniela Kocelli

Guido Orzes

Alessandro Narduzzo

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #1	
Reference Person	Margherita Molinaro
Key-descriptors	
Title	Special track on “Innovative Engineering Education” at the 3 rd ISIEA Conference
TAGS	#Innovative Education #Engineering #Learning Factories
Date	20.06.2024
Participants	7 presenters of scientific research papers/abstracts on “Innovative Engineering Education” and around 15-20 participants as audience
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The special track “Innovative Engineering Education” was organized within the 3rd <i>International Symposium on Industrial Engineering and Automation (ISIEA)</i>, an international scientific conference (with proceedings published as a volume of Springer’s Lecture Notes) dealing with different Engineering topics. The topic of the 2024 edition was Latest Advancements in Mechanical Engineering. Two participation modalities were foreseen by the conference:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Submission of Full Papers, with recommended length of 8 pages in Springer format that, if accepted, could be published in the conference proceedings. The work was presented with a 15-minutes talk. - Submission of Extended Abstracts of a maximum of 2 pages; a 15-minutes talk was foreseen for this modality as well. <p>The special track “Innovative Engineering Education” was organized in collaboration with two external experts of engineering education, Prof. Bernd Zunk (Technical University of Graz) and Dr. Manuel Woschank (Montanuniversität Leoben).</p> <p>Organizing the special track involved various preparatory activities. In addition to promoting the initiative, it was essential to coordinate closely with the conference organizers to identify and assign reviewers for submitted papers and abstracts. Each full paper was reviewed by two reviewers, while each extended abstract received one review. Throughout the review process, representatives from different universities and countries were involved.</p> <p>Overall, the special track was a success—one of the largest at the conference—and featured 7 contributions: 4 full papers and 3 extended abstracts. All submissions were accepted following the review process. The authors represented a diverse range of institutions, including the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, University of Bologna, Polytechnic University of Bari, Czech Technical University in Prague, Sapienza University of Rome, University of Twente, The Business Game, Graz University of Technology, and Europa-Universität Flensburg.</p> <p>The papers covered a variety of topics, from broader themes in technical education to more specialized issues related to education in management and mechanical engineering. Further details on titles and authors of the 7 participating papers are provided below.</p> <p>Title 1: Technology in engineering education: the sustainable enterprise business game Authors: Fontanella Sabrina, Fraccascia Luca, Nonino Fabio, Baldissin Nicola</p> <p>Title 2: The certification of an entrepreneurship competence during an interfaculty business challenge Authors: Morselli Daniele, Luppi Elena, Ricci Aurora, Parricchi Monica</p> <p>Title 3: Criticism and proposal of a model for the design and rapid set-up of a training course based on 3D printing Authors: Scibilia Sergio & Casalino Giuseppe</p> <p>Title 4: A Unity3D-based interactive educational game of compressed air system maintenance Authors: Isik Birkan, Emir Isik Gulbahar, Zilka Miroslav</p> <p>Title 5: The role of Nordic entrepreneurship education for technical education</p>

	<p>Authors: Schild Katharina & Morselli Daniele</p> <p>Title 6: Data Spaces for Leading Future Innovation Processes Authors: Pichler Rudolf & Schellander Martin</p> <p>Title 7: Blended Intensive Programmes as effective and innovative solutions to train the engineers of the future Authors: Molinaro Margherita, Orzes Guido, Borgianni Yuri</p> <p>The ISIEA 2024 conference was held from June 19th to 21st, 2024, in Bolzano at the NOI Techpark. The special track on “Innovative Engineering Education” took place on Thursday, June 20th, with presentations divided into a morning and an afternoon session. The track chairs of the two sessions were respectively Prof. Guido Orzes and Dr. Margherita Molinaro (both from the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano).</p> <p>Audience participation was strong, although it’s difficult to provide an exact count since conference attendees often join specific presentations rather than entire sessions. Nonetheless, around 15–20 attendees were always present for this track, with some coming from outside Europe. The presentations led to engaging discussions and fruitful exchanges of ideas among participants.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	iNEST professors and researchers (in particular in the Engineering field) belonging to all the Spokes were invited to present a paper or attend the special track on Innovative Engineering Education. Different tools were used to advertise the special track, including official conference website, iNEST website and personal emails.
Website/link	<p>The conference website (https://isiea.events.unibz.it/) has been updated with the new edition of ISIEA (2025), therefore data and information on the special track “Innovative Engineering Education” may not be fully available (even though there is a special page dedicated to the 2024 edition: PREVIOUS EDITIONS → 2024 – 3rd Edition).</p> <p>The Springer book including the proceedings of the conference is available here: https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-031-70462-8 (Volume 1) and https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-031-70465-9 (Volume 2).</p>
Notes	
Images from the event	<p>Screenshot of the Call for Papers of ISIEA2024 with the description of the special track.</p>

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #2	
Reference Persons	Paola Venuti, Anna Serbati
Key-descriptors	
Title	Students' wellbeing and inclusive education at university
TAGS	Students' wellbeing, inclusion, prevention, higher education
Date	13 March 2024
Participants	21
Details	
Description of event and programme	To our knowledge, most of the research on university students' health has focused on examining the prevalence of distress and on the student's use of support services when experiencing mental health difficulties. However, less research has focused on preventive measures that universities could take to reduce environmental stressors and promote students' well-being in the university environment.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event was promoted internally at the University of Trento through email invitations and advertisements on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	
	The seminar was devoted to all academics and students' representatives

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #2	
Reference Persons	Paola Venuti, Anna Serbati
Key-descriptors	
Title	Educational leadership at university
TAGS	Educational leadership, management, teaching and learning innovation, quality assurance
Date	10 January 2023, 10 June 2023
Participants	19
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>As the international literature underlines (Bolander Laksov, 2017; 2021) middle-management staff, delegates, and department heads are crucial to promote the success of developmental programs for the innovation of teaching, learning and assessment processes in University.</p> <p>As a result, it becomes important for institutional leaders to participate in advanced training courses that will enable them to contribute to the development of a high-quality learning and assessment environment in their context.</p> <p>Starting from the literature evidence, two seminars devoted to course coordinators and teaching delegates will be organized:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two days workshop for course coordinators: this initiative will include an introductory theoretical part dedicated to the topic of educational leadership with experts on the subject: reflective activities will be proposed through group work based on the cooperative learning technique. Specifically, the first part of the workshop will address the national regulatory directions and the duties of course coordinators in the framework of AVA3 standards. The second part will focus on active and innovative teaching and learning methodologies, also in connection with the specificity of their educational leadership role as course coordinators • Two days workshop for teaching delegates: this initiative will include an introductory theoretical part dedicated to the topic of educational leadership with experts on the subject. Participants will be invited to develop a personal structured reflection on their practice (with the adoption of specific tools), starting from a problematic issue related to their practice or specific tasks connected to their role. After the individual reflection, teaching delegates will be invited to discuss their experiences in pairs/groups and then with the class groups. An important part of this program will be based on the power of sharing practices connected to the teaching delegates activities in their departments. During the two days workshop, teaching delegates will be able to understand and reflect on specific techniques, such as reflective team and mentoring approach, to be exported and adopted in their departments
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The events were promoted internally in the University Ateneum through mail invitation, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	
	The seminars were devoted to departmental teaching delegates and course coordinators

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #4	
Reference Person	Susanna Pisciella, Elena Giacomello, Francesco Trovò
Key-descriptors	
Title	Spoke 4 workshop series: Living off-grid, designing the transition
TAGS	Off-grid living, autonomy, sustainable architecture
Date	23 – 27 September 2024
Participants	27 luav students
Details	
Description of event and programme	The workshop was aligned with the decarbonization goals of the European Green Deal, focusing on achieving climate neutrality by 2050. It aimed to enhance the self-sufficiency of single-family homes in the North-East through energy, water, and food autonomy. Participants explored solutions for energy efficiency, water management, and food production, integrating both technological and architectural approaches. The workshop also incorporated historical building techniques to increase architectural value and improve territorial resilience, using designs and models as key tools. Professors: Susanna Pisciella, Elena Giacomello, Francesco Trovò. Tutor: Alioscia Mozzato.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The workshop focused on innovative solutions for energy efficiency in existing building stock. In the frame of iNEST the initiatives aimed to tackle environmental risks (such as seismic and hydraulic) through proactive design approaches, addressing the urgent need for deep renovation and energy transition.
Website/link	https://www.consorziointest.it/verso-la-neutralita-climatica-progettare-una-transizione-sostenibile-ed-equa/
Criteria for Participation	
Requirements	luav students of Architecture (both Bachelor or Master Degree)
Images from the event	</p>

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects

SPOKE #4

Reference Person Daniela Ruggeri

Key-descriptors

Title **Spoke 4 workshop series: Water and energy: two elements for a unified project**

TAGS Water-energy nexus, climate adaptation, hydrogeological challenges

Date 23 – 27 September 2024

Participants 11 luav students

Details

Description of event and programme The workshop explored the relationship between the Piave river basin’s hydroelectric infrastructure and its hydrogeological challenges, considering the region’s historical use of water for energy. It aimed to develop architectural solutions addressing water and energy in the context of the energy transition. Participants worked across diverse spatial conditions within the 220 km basin, identifying key local stakeholders and issues. The final outcomes were shared and discussed collectively at the workshop’s conclusion.
Professor: Daniela Ruggeri. Tutor: Matteo Vianello.

Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST The workshop aligned with iNEST’s objectives by focusing on sustainable solutions for the Piave basin’s hydroelectric infrastructure and hydrogeological issues. It emphasized hands-on experimentation with low-carbon materials to develop energy-efficient designs, integrating both historical and environmental considerations. The collaborative outcomes contributed to iNEST’s mission of enhancing sustainable construction practices.

Website/link <https://www.consorziointest.it/verso-la-neutralita-climatica-progettare-una-transizione-sostenibile-ed-equa/>

Criteria for Participation

Requirements luav students of Architecture (both Bachelor or Master Degree)

Images from the event

Acqua ed energia: due elementi per un progetto unitario
Docenti: Daniela Ruggeri
Tutor: Matteo Vianello

23 - 27 settembre 2024 | Aula M1 Cotonificio Università Iuav di Venezia | Presentazione finale dei lavori venerdì 27 settembre 2024 a partire dalle ore 14:00 nelle aule L1, L2, M1, M2

Il workshop è volto a investigare scenari e progetti basati sulla coesistenza tra ecologie fluviali e reti dell'energia, un rapporto di lunga durata che nel Piave diventa paradigmatico. È in risposta necessaria oggi di essere eletto alla luce dei cambiamenti climatici e delle nuove direttive dell'UE in materia di neutralità climatica. Il bacino del Piave e gli spazi dell'energia diventano occasione per esplorare nuovi approcci progettuali nell'epoca della transizione energetica. Il workshop intende sviluppare progetti che possano in maniera mediata e contestualizzare forme di produzione energetica in armonia con l'ecologia fluviale.

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Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects

SPOKE #4		
Reference Person	Rosaria Revellini, Valeria Tatano, Cristiana Cellucci	
Key-descriptors		
Title	Spoke 4 workshop series: Inclusive move/ability	
TAGS	spatial dynamics in urban areas, urban accessibility	
Date	23 – 27 September 2024	
Participants	18 luav students	
Details		
Description of event and programme	<p>Within the iNEST research framework, the workshop targeted Architecture and Urban Planning students to explore topics rarely covered in regular courses. It focused on accessibility, movement, and spatial dynamics in urban areas, addressing challenges related to climate change and sustainable energy transition. The aim was to consider diverse human needs and their extensions (like walkers or strollers) in public spaces. Activities included field surveys, spatial mapping, and graphical solutions for mobility challenges. The output consisted of a digital booklet and a presentation board summarizing the findings, which were discussed on the final day.</p> <p>Professors: Rosaria Revellini, Valeria Tatano, Cristiana Cellucci</p>	
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The workshop aligned with iNEST's focus by investigating sustainable urban mobility within Metropolitan City of Venice. It addressed inclusivity, accessibility, and energy transition challenges, emphasizing practical solutions that consider diverse user needs and climate resilience.	
Website/link	https://www.consorziointest.it/verso-la-neutralita-climatica-progettare-una-transizione-sostenibile-ed-equa/	
Criteria for Participation		
Requirements	luav students of Architecture (Bachelor Degree) and Urban Planning (both Bachelor or Master Degree)	
Image(s) from the event	<p>Inclusive move/ability</p> <p>Docenti: Rosaria Revellini, Valeria Tatano, Cristiana Cellucci</p> <p>23 - 27 settembre 2024</p> <p>Aula M2 Ca' Sagredo Università Iuav di Venezia</p> <p>Presentazione finale dei lavori venerdì 27 settembre 2024 a partire dalle ore 14:00 nelle aule L1, L2, M1, M2</p> <p>Il workshop connette i temi propri dell'accessibilità ambientale con le sfide del Green Deal europeo. Obiettivo è quello di osservare situazioni in che molti rilevanti oggi: umane e le relative "ostacoli" (posizione, carattere, i) e relazione con gli spazi aperti delle città e comprendere quali sono gli ostacoli alla mobilità presenti, non solo in termini di limiti fisici (es. mancanza di spazi adeguati) ma anche di problematiche in caso di eventi di mutati climatici. A partire da un caso studio reale, verranno analizzate le principali criticità e ipotizzate soluzioni progettuali innovative per una inclusiva mobility.</p> <p>CC4 Iuav Venezia</p>	

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #4	
Reference Person	Elisa Zatta, Massimiliano Condotta, DEMOGO studio
Key-descriptors	
Title	Spoke 4 workshop series: Renewable + Recycled = Rebuilt
TAGS	Low-carbon construction, new materials, circular constructions
Date	23 – 27 September 2024
Participants	18 luav students
Details	
Description of event and programme	The workshop aimed to rethink construction practices to reduce the environmental impact of the building sector by exploring sustainable, renewable, and circular materials. It focused on practical design exercises using engineered wood, plant-based materials, and recycled aggregate concrete. Participants worked in small groups to reimagine an existing building with low-carbon construction techniques, developing scalable models and presenting their findings on the final day. The approach emphasized innovative uses of renewable resources to create sustainable construction methods that enhance energy, functional, and structural efficiency. Professors: Elisa Zatta, Massimiliano Condotta, DEMOGO studio. Tutor: Alice Rampazzo.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The workshop aligns with iNEST's goals by exploring sustainable construction practices through hands-on experimentation. It focused on using circular, renewable, and low-carbon materials to enhance energy efficiency and functionality in existing buildings. The initiative emphasizes practical applications in line with iNEST's mission to drive sustainable architectural practices in the Venice region.
Website/link	https://www.consorziointest.it/verso-la-neutralita-climatica-progettare-una-transizione-sostenibile-ed-equa/
Criteria for Participation	
Requirements	luav students of Architecture (both Bachelor or Master Degree)
Image(s) from the event	<p>RENEWABLE + RECYCLED = REBUILT</p> <p>Docenti: Elisa Zatta, Massimiliano Condotta, DEMOGO Tutor: Alice Rampazzo</p> <p>23 - 27 settembre 2024</p> <p>Aula L1 Catonificio Università luav di Venezia</p> <p>Presentazione finale dei lavori venerdì 27 settembre 2024 a partire dalle ore 14:00 nelle aule L1, L2, M1, M2</p> <p>Quali sistemi costruttivi sperimentare per le nuove costruzioni e per un patrimonio edilizio bisognoso di efficiente merito energetico, funzionale e strutturale? Come possono le risorse rinnovabili e circolari essere uno strumento del progettista nel formulare un nuovo modo di costruire? Il workshop guiderà gli studenti nell'explorare soluzioni tecnologiche volte a ripensare un edificio esistente. Ciascun gruppo lavorerà su un modello sostenibile in scala 1:50, sperimentando le possibili alterazioni volumetriche, spaziali, distributive e formali consentite da materiali e sistemi costruttivi low-carbon.</p> <p>CC4 iNEST al centro dell'innovazione</p> <p>Università luav di Venezia</p>

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Andrea Gerosa
Key-descriptors	
Title	Integrare le competenze di sostenibilità nei percorsi formativi tecnologici e scientifici
TAGS	Training path, sustainability, technology and scientific university programmes
Date	11 September 2024
Participants	30 professors and PhD students
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>Sustainability is a fundamental target in most of the working and production scenarios, in which our students will be involved. Thus, it is important to develop the right way to involve and attract them with respect to sustainability issues.</p> <p>This interactive seminar aims to guide participants to identify the transversal skills relevant to their own context and to design the corresponding experiential learning activities using the 3T PLAY trident framework. Using this framework will ensure that the developed activity includes the three essential aspects for robust skill development: Knowing, Experiencing and Learning from Experience.</p> <p>An example of a 3T PLAY activity “How to support students to develop skills that promote sustainability” will be presented to the participants, providing them with the open-source material needed for future facilitations.</p> <p>This workshop is part of the 3T PLAY project, which mission is to develop the next generation of tangibles-based learning activities to teach STEM and engineering students the transversal skills needed to bring sustainable and ethical principles in their profession.</p> <p>Workshop outcomes:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Understand the relevance of the 3T PLAY Trident Framework for designing transversal skills activities 2. Identify relevant transversal skills for your students/your context 3. Design a prototype of an activity based on the trident framework to develop students' level for these skills <p>This workshop is open to head of institutions, teachers and educators</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event was promoted through the web pages of the iNEST Consortium and the University of Trieste. The program was sent to all iNEST Spokes, who shared the communication in their networks. Furthermore, other national universities were informed.
Website/link	
Notes	
Remark	This Seminar substitutes the event “Tools for MOOC elaboration: Workshop on innovative LightBoard”, which was mentioned in the original scheduling of activities

Image from the event

Integrare le competenze di sostenibilità nei percorsi formativi tecnologici e scientifici

Mercoledì 11/09/2024
ore 9:00

Aula magna A. Lepschy
Dipartimento di ingegneria
dell'informazione (DEI)

Via Gradenigo 6/b
Padova

Presentazione

In un momento storico in cui la **sostenibilità** diviene un obiettivo imprescindibile nella maggior parte dei contesti produttivi e lavorativi in cui saranno coinvolti i nostri laureati, ci chiediamo quanto effettivamente gli studenti e le studentesse di corsi di studio ingegneristici (e scientifici in generale) siano stimolati a **sviluppare una corretta sensibilità** rispetto alle tematiche legate alla sostenibilità e quanto i percorsi formativi loro proposti abbiano tra gli obiettivi quello di **far acquisire competenze di sostenibilità**. Con questo incontro, desideriamo aprire un confronto e stimolare una riflessione condivisa su quali possano essere metodologie didattiche e contenuti che, integrati nell'usuale offerta formativa, stimolino negli studenti e nelle studentesse la consapevolezza di quanto le tematiche della sostenibilità siano cruciali, permettendo loro di acquisire le relative competenze fondamentali.

L'intervento principale di questo incontro è rappresentato dal **seminario della dott.ssa Valentina Rossi**, consulente pedagogico presso Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Lausanne (EPFL): per maggiori dettagli rispetto al suo intervento, si invita a leggere la presentazione allegata.

Programma

10 min	Saluti istituzionali e introduzione
10 min	A. Gerosa Problem Solving e Pensiero Sistemico: due competenze trasversali per l'ingegneria che conducono alla sostenibilità
30 min	Valentina Rossi (EPFL) Design your own Transversal Skills Activities with the 3T PLAY Trident Framework
15 min	Domande e dibattito

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Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #6	
Reference Person	Alessandro Cinquegrani
Key-descriptors	
Title	Special track on “Innovative Engineering Education” at the 3rd ISIEA Conference (formerly: A Literary Exploration of Entrepreneurial Culture in the iNest Ecosystem)
TAGS	#Innovative Education #Engineering #Learning Factories
Date	26 January 2024
Participants	80
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>Il convegno è stato promosso da promosso da iNest - Interconnected Nord Est Innovation Ecosystem e dall’Associazione Amici di Comisso di Treviso per favorire una riflessione sulla cultura letteraria veneta, con la collaborazione della Camera di Commercio Treviso Belluno Dolomiti, Confindustria Veneto Est e il patrocinio del Comune di Treviso e dell’Università Ca’ Foscari di Venezia con il suo Dipartimento di Studi Umanistici.</p> <p>L’incontro aperto al pubblico si è tenuto venerdì 26 gennaio dalla 10 alle 18 a Palazzo Giacomelli – Spazio Confindustria Veneto Est a Treviso (piazza Garibaldi 13) ed è organizzato e diretto da Alessandro Cinquegrani, Professore ordinario di Letteratura italiana contemporanea all’Università Ca’ Foscari e da Gianluigi Bodi, fondatore del blog senzaudio.it.</p> <p>Venetarium 2 è incentrato sui temi Letteratura Impresa Lavoro, fattori che spesso nella narrazione e il senso comune connotano il Veneto e i veneti.</p> <p>“In Veneto – spiegano Alessandro Cinquegrani e Gianluigi Bodi - esisteva un conflitto tra il mondo economico, focalizzato su lavoro e profitto, e quello umanistico, fondato su una nobile inutilità. Da alcuni anni, tuttavia, questo conflitto sembra volto se non a una soluzione almeno a una ridefinizione.</p> <p>Siamo nel cuore del cambiamento: le imprese cercano collaborazioni da artisti e scrittori e gli scrittori guardano con rinnovata curiosità a questo mondo. È perciò il tempo di interrogarci sul rapporto tra letteratura, impresa e lavoro, da prospettive diverse: a che punto siamo rispetto al conflitto di un tempo? Se ne sentono ancora le conseguenze o viviamo nel mezzo di un’epoca nuova segnata da un’inedita sinergia? Il convegno proverà a rispondere a queste domande”.</p> <p>Letteratura e lavoro è stato il titolo della sessione mattutina, introdotta da Alessandro Cinquegrani. Micro Artuso leggerà poi brani di Works di Vitaliano Trevisan (a due anni dalla scomparsa dello scrittore vicentino e in occasione della riedizione nella Trilogia di Thomas di Einaudi delle sue prime opere). Seguiranno gli interventi di Romolo Bugaro (Nordest e lavoro), Giulio Mozzi (Il lavoro nell’editoria) e Antonio Bortoluzzi (Come si fanno le cose – L’etica del lavoro).</p> <p>La sessione pomeridiana guardava invece a Letteratura e impresa, con i dialoghi tra Giuseppe Lupo e Fabrizio Panozzo (Le narrazioni dell’impresa nel Novecento), Ginevra Amadio ed Elisa Gera (La fabbrica della bellezza), Renzo di Renzo e Valentina Durante (Narrazioni al plurale) e l’intervento di Fulvio Ervas Scrivere gialli sull’imprenditoria veneta.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	
Website/link	https://pric.unive.it/progetti/spoke-6-inest/bandi-e-news
Notes	

Images from the event

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #8	
Reference Person	Donata Vianelli, Alberto Marinò
Key-descriptors	
Title	Summer School in Sustainability and Digitalization in the Blue Economy
TAGS	Sustainability, Digitalization, Blue Economy, Ports, Shipyards, Transport Systems, Logistics, Maritime Industry, Energy.
Date	July 14 – 20, 2024
Participants	28 Master's and PhD students in the scientific and social-economic sciences
Details	
Description of event and programme	The Summer School, organized at the University of Trieste, represents a multidisciplinary full immersion in sustainability and digitalization, offering students a transversal in-depth analysis of scientific, technological, and economic topics applied to the Blue Economy. The program has covered problems, impacts, and opportunities that ports, shipyards, transport and logistic operators, and the maritime industry face from the perspective of digitalization and sustainability. The teaching methodology will include frontal lessons, teamwork, and company visits. The detailed program is described below:

	<p>14 luglio, domenica</p> <p>Arrivo dei partecipanti a Trieste e sistemazione nei residence</p> <p>15 luglio, lunedì</p> <p>9.00 – 9.30 Saluti istituzionali, Pierluigi Barbieri, Cristina Pedicchio, Donata Vianelli, Giorgio Sulligoi, Alberto Marinò</p> <p>9.30 – 11.00 Sostenibilità e digitalizzazione nei sistemi portuali, Romeo Danielis</p> <p>11.30 – 12.15 Intermodalità mare-terra nei porti, Giovanni Longo</p> <p>12.15 – 13.00 Porti e decarbonizzazione nella prospettiva economica: sfide e opportunità, Giuseppe Borruso</p> <p>13.00 – 13.45 pranzo</p> <p>14.00 – 15.30 Strategie per l'incremento della sostenibilità del trasporto marittimo verso la decarbonizzazione dei mezzi navali, Vittorio Bucci, Luca Braidotti e Alberto Marinò</p> <p> Evoluzione digitale dei processi di progettazione e produzione navale, Vittorio Bucci, Serena Bertagna e Alberto Marinò</p> <p>16.00 – 17.30 La trasformazione digitale dell'energia e i sistemi marini, Andrea Alessia Tavagnutti e Giorgio Sulligoi</p> <p>18.30 – 19.30 <i>Incontro conviviale e di networking - Club Nautico Triestino Sirena</i></p> <p>16 luglio, martedì</p> <p>8.30 Ritrovo e partenza Pullman in Stazione autobus, Largo Città di Santos, Trieste</p> <p>9.00 – 12.30 Visita al Porto di Trieste. Accompagnatori: Giovanni Longo e Alberto Marinò</p> <p>13.00 – 13.45 pranzo e partenza da UNITS con il pullman alle 13.50</p> <p>14.30 – 17.30 Visita Groupe Beneteau Italia, Monfalcone (GO). Accompagnatori: Alberto Marinò e Donata Vianelli</p> <p>17 luglio, mercoledì</p> <p>9.00 – 10.30 Il Copernicus Marine Service, Stefano Salon e Gianpiero Cossarini</p> <p>11.00 – 12.30 Dal Copernicus Marine Service al Digital Twin del nord Adriatico, Stefano Querin</p> <p>12.30 – 13.30 pranzo e partenza da UNITS con il pullman alle 13.40</p> <p>14.15 – 15.45 Visita all'Acquedotto "Giovanni Randaccio" di San Giovanni di Duino</p> <p>16.30 – 18.00 Visita al Depuratore di Servola – AcegasApsAmga Accompagnatori: Daniele Bosich e Alberto Marinò</p> <p>18 luglio, giovedì</p> <p>9.00 – 10.30 Introduzione alle reti neurali,</p> <p>11.00 – 12.30 Machine Learning per i Digital Twins: applicazioni alla Blue Economy, Luca Manzoni</p> <p>12.30 – 13.30 pranzo e partenza da UNITS con il pullman alle 13.40</p> <p>14.30 – 17.30 Visita allo Stabilimento di Monfalcone di Fincantieri SpA Accompagnatori: Alberto Marinò e Donata Vianelli</p> <p>19.30 – 21.00 <i>Incontro conviviale e di networking - Società Triestina della Vela</i></p> <p>19 luglio, venerdì</p> <p>9.00 – 13.00 Workshop e Team working "Laboratorio di futuro per anticipare gli impatti della Twin Transition nella Blue Economy", Andrea Giacomelli e Chiara Ambro</p> <p>13.00 – 14.00 pranzo</p> <p>14.00 – 16.00 Presentazioni finali e conclusione dei lavori con consegna degli attestati di partecipazione e di valutazione, Andrea Giacomelli, Chiara Ambrosi, Alberto Marinò, Giorgio Sulligoi, Donata Vianelli</p> <p>20 luglio, sabato</p> <p>Check-out dal residence e rientro dei partecipanti da Trieste</p> <p>La Summer School INEST è finanziata dal Piano Nazionale per la Ripresa e Resilienza (PNRR) Missione 4 Componente 2 Investimento 1.5. Creazione e rafforzamento di "Ecosistemi dell'innovazione per la sostenibilità" progetto "iNEST – Interconnected Nord-Est Innovation Ecosystem", Attività trasversali CC4 Cross-Cutting Activity CC4 "Education & Lifelong Learning" - CUP J43C22000320006 - Finanziato dall'Unione Europea, NextGenerationEU</p> <p>Organizzato da Università degli Studi di Trieste in collaborazione con:</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Autorità di Sistema Portuale del Mare Adriatico Orientale Porti di Trieste e Monfalcone</p> </div> </div>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event was promoted through the web pages of the iNEST Consortium and the University of Trieste. The program was sent to all iNEST Spokes, who shared the communication in their networks. Furthermore, other national universities were informed.
Website/link	https://www.consorzioinest.it/sostenibilita-e-digitalizzazione-nella-blue-economy/ https://portale.units.it/en/events/sustainability-and-digitalization-blue-economy#:~:text=July%2014%20%2D%2020%2C%202024%20%2D,applied%20to%20Blue%20Economy%20sectors.
Notes	

Images from the event

MISSIONE 4
ISTRUZIONE
RICERCA

Interconnected Nord-Est
Innovation Ecosystem

Cross-Cutting Activity #4

Education
& Lifelong Learning

i NEST

Annex 2

Minors & Challenges

***Performed
in the frame of
Milestone #27***

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #2	
Reference Person	Nicola Doppio, Hub Innovazione Trentino
Key-descriptors	
Title	Meditech Challenge – Vascular Surgery
TAGS	Medical Industry, Technology, Vascular Surgery
Date	February 2024 – May 2024
Participants	45
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The Meditech Challenge – Vascular Surgery is an initiative aimed at accelerating the transfer of scientific and technological knowledge between academia, clinical practice and the medical tech industry. It connects PhD and MSc students affiliated with various departments of the University of Trento with specializing doctors in vascular surgery from across Italy with the aim to tackle the challenges faced by vascular surgeons in their everyday clinical practice. Students and specializing doctors will form multidisciplinary teams that will develop ideas and plans for PoC – Proof of Concept solutions to technological-related challenges pre-selected by a commission of vascular surgeons and university professors, also taking into account insight from the medical tech industry. Topics, knowledge and abilities to be achieved during the Challenge will relate to the: 1) design of customized prostheses (stents) produced with innovative materials and processes such as to allow adaptation to different anatomies; 2) design of smart stents, systems or processes capable of minimizing or preventing the occurrence of type 1 endoleaks; 3) design of systems capable of reducing exposure to X-rays of patient and surgeon during surgery; 4) design of smart stents, systems or processes capable of minimizing or preventing the occurrence of type 2 endoleaks; 5) creation of robots capable of innovating the process and practices of surgical interventions; 6) systems to support the intelligent and optimal planning and execution of surgical interventions.</p> <p>Medical tech companies (large manufacturers of prostheses, stents and devices) will be involved as sponsors.</p> <p>The initiative is co-organized by HIT, DISI – Department of Information Science and Engineering of the University of Trento, and APSS - the Provincial Agency for Health Services of the Autonomous Province of Trento (APSS).</p> <p>Participants will be involved in activities such as data acquisition; data analysis with advanced software; modeling of phenomena and processes; access to laboratories for the use of machinery; carrying out of experimental tests; field observation; design and engineering of prototypes; reporting and presentations to expert juries, including researchers, vascular surgeons, and leading companies from the medical engineering sector. Teams’ collaboration will be supervised by HIT and mentored by UniTN professors, as well as senior vascular surgeons. Kickoff meeting is scheduled on February 7, 2024; the final event is scheduled on 15 May 2024.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event was promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	https://webmagazine.unitn.it/news/disi/116857/meditech-challenge-chirurgia-vascolare-2023
Notes	
Requirements	Requirement for participating to the Challenge as a “solver” is to be a PhD or MSc student affiliated with any department of the University of Trento; or: being a specializing doctor (aka “resident doctor”) in vascular surgery, from whatever institution across Italy.

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #2	
Reference Person	Roberto Napoli
Key-descriptors	
Title	SOI-123 Challenge 3: MEC-La magia della pietra a spacco
TAGS	Machines, stone splitting
Date	October – December 2023
Participants	16
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>A pure market challenge that MEC, a company known for its commitment to innovation driven by young and brilliant minds, is launching at various Italian universities.</p> <p>Challenge statement: What new technologies (e.g., lasers, connectivity) can be applied to innovate MEC's stone cutting/splitting machines in the next 10 years, and what new technologies (e.g., generative artificial intelligence, virtual configurators, e-commerce channels, virtual assistants) can help MEC communicate the magic of stone splitting to customers and partners (e.g., architects, construction companies, interior designers) in international markets, creating a customer experience (pre and post-sales consulting services) consistent with a boutique of simple and highly functional products, where technology still serves humanity, and the human aspect prevails in the human-machine interaction?</p> <p>Challenge Based Learning: kick off, mentorships, draft projects evaluations, final presentation to the company team and prize allocation.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event was promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	https://www.mecs.it/en/about-us https://www.soi.unitn.it/courses/soi-123-mec-la-magia-della-pietra-a-spacco/
Notes	
Description of eventual requirements	Students from all disciplines enrolled at the University of Trento, LIUC in Castellanza, or LUM-Libera Università Mediterranea were eligible. Both individual and team applications have been accepted. Teams have been formed based on the criterion of diversity, including field of study, background and experiences.

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #2	
Reference Person	Nicola Doppio (HIT)
Key-descriptors	
Title	Innovation Challenges supporting higher education and research-industry open innovation
TAGS	Open Innovation, Research, Industry, Higher Education
Date	4 and 16 July 2024
Participants	18
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>Webinar 1: provision of concepts and examples</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What is open innovation ● Short history of innovation prizes, contests and challenges ● Examples of Innovation Challenge formats ● How an Innovation Challenge works ● Guidelines, hints and tips to manage a successful Innovation Challenge ● How to design a new Innovation Challenge ● The Innovation Challenge Design Canvas ● European projects about Innovation Challenges ● Q&A <p>Webinar 2: hands on session (max 20 participants)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Deep dive into the 12 blocks of the Innovation Challenge Design Canvas ● Assignment: start designing your own Innovation Challenge ● Presentations and discussion <p>At the end of the course participants have been able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● describe the difference between the various types of innovation prizes, contests and challenges; ● recognize the input-output model of a Technological Innovation Challenge; ● discuss the main guidelines for implementing a successful Innovation Challenge; ● identify what are the structural elements of an Innovation Challenge; <p>formulate new concepts of Innovation Challenge tailored to own goals and ecosystems.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event was promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	https://www.innochallenge-project.eu/
Notes	
Description of eventual requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Professors and researchers interested in CBL – Challenge-Based Learning ● Researchers & scientists willing to boost their knowledge transfer capabilities ● Innovation managers and technology transfer officers ● Research project managers ● Companies' R&D staff ● Policy makers

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #3	
Reference Person	Gian Luca Foresti, Pier Luca Montessoro, Luca Di Gaspero
Key-descriptors	
Title	self-assessment tools for ICT courses
TAGS	
Date	October 2023 – September 2025
Participants	
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>This project involves the development of various self-assessment tools as part of courses in the ICT sector such as: Fundamentals of Computer Programming, Data Structures and Algorithms, Logical Networks, Computer Architecture, Operating Systems, Computer Networks.</p> <p>During the period from October 2023 to September 2024, the following activities were undertaken:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of the technical specifications for the framework within which self-learning and self-assessment modules will be developed. This included identifying the technological requirements, setting goals for interactivity, and ensuring that the framework supports adaptability to different learning needs. • Development of educational content specific to each subject involved in the project. This process aimed to ensure that the learning materials will be accurate, engaging, and aligned with current educational standards and practices. • Establishment of formal requirements for outsourcing the development work to an external company through a public tender. This involved preparing detailed guidelines, evaluation criteria, and other formal aspects to ensure transparency and fairness in the selection process. <p>Initiation of the public tender procedure to carry out the process of engaging an external developer. This stage included announcing the tender, managing communications with interested vendors, and organizing the assessment procedures to select the most qualified provider.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event was promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	https://elearning.uniud.it/moodle/login/index.php (please send an email to pierluca.montessoro@uniud.it for a guest account)
Criteria for Certification	
Notes	Self-assessment tools will be developed to cover all the topics of the courses and will be organized in a path of increasing hardness and depth, to provide users a trajectory of continuous learning from the basic knowledge to the more advance strategies.

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #3	
Reference Person	Gian Luca Foresti, Francesca Zanon
Key-descriptors	
Title	Video Analysis and Teacher Training
TAGS	
Duration	October 2023 – September 2025
Participants	20/30 university teachers 50 students
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>In line with the developments in teacher training approaches, the most recent literature emphasizes the potential of video analysis in promoting the professional vision of teachers. In particular, by offering the opportunity for a “second-hand” experience of teaching through the immersion in authentic classroom situations captured in their richness and complexity, video analysis can foster the development of noticing and reasoning skills supported by a process of recursive interaction between theory and practice.</p> <p>The project pursues the following aims:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Develop a system of methodologies, tools and procedures for video analysis to foster the improvement of the teaching skills of university teachers - Test the system within a pilot training course aimed at UniUD teachers <p>Below are all the activities carried out.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. As a first approach to the use of video analysis in learning contexts it was a detailed simulation activity was organized to introduce the teaching of fractions in primary school carried out with some students of the Educational Technologies course. <p>The activity took place in the 10 hours scheduled for the laboratory part of the course and were all the suitable design tools and aids have been prepared by the laboratory representatives to the simulation activity. The activity was video-recorded and subsequently analyzed also discussed with the students. Reflection and evaluation questionnaires were prepared regarding the activity in order to be able to control the outcomes compared to the initial objectives.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. The activity was subsequently the subject of reflection which led to the production of an article that is currently under review in the journal “Orientamenti Pedagogici”. 3. The LID is collaborating with the faculty of Agricultural Sciences to support reflection needs on disciplinary teaching in the scientific field emerged in this faculty from some teachers. <p>After two meetings with agricultural science teachers to define the training needs it was designed the teaching support including some video recordings of discipline lessons scientific. The scientific bibliography was analyzed by the teachers belonging to the LID could constitute a reference for the detailed analysis of the recordings and for the subsequent one discussion with interested teachers. Also at the conclusion of this activity research/training the production of at least one scientific article is expected</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event was promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	
Evaluation methods	Implementation of the pilot course aimed at SFP (DILL) teachers and evaluation of the effectiveness of the video-based training model proposed through a one-group pre-/post-test design (initial and final assessment to measure the learning outcomes of the course in terms of changes in the beliefs, knowledge and skills of the participating university teachers).

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #3	
Reference Person	Gian Luca Foresti, Luca Casarsa
Key-descriptors	
Title	E-Racing Team
TAGS	Formula Student, Electric car, Formula Electric
Date	1 st October 2023 – 30 September 2024
Participants	42 students from Bachelor or Master courses of the University of Udine , and in particular: Mechanical Engineering, Electrical Engineering, Managerial Engineering, Computer Science, Economics, International Marketing and Organization, Multimedia Science and Technology.
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The aim of the project is to provide to the participating student the opportunity to develop a complete engineering project, with the final purpose to design, produce and test an electric competition vehicle to participate to the Formula Students championship.</p> <p>By their participation to the projects, the students have the opportunities to empowering their engineering skills and acquire new soft skill that will be surely useful for a faster and smoother entry into their professional life</p> <p>During the period from October 2023 and September 2024, the students were divided in different working groups with specific tasks and accordingly with their curricula of study: Aerodynamic Department; Vehicle Dynamics Department, Electronics and Firmware Department, Power Train Department, Business Department, and Marketing Department. Each Department work was coordinated by s responsible, the overall team work was supervised by a Team Leader and a Technical Officer.</p> <p>A new racing car was designed and built in 6 months, in order to have it ready to compete in the 2024 Formula Student events. Also, a complete business plan and cost report were also elaborated by the students, as requested by the competition rules.</p> <p>The team participated at two events: Formula Student Germany, Hockenheim circuit, 13-18 August 2024 Formula SAE Italy, Riccardo Paletti circuit, Varano de Melegari (PR), 3-8 Settembre 2024</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event was promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	https://formulasae.uniud.it/ https://www.formula-ata.it/ https://www.formulastudent.de/fsg/
Notes	
CFU delivered	<p>The number of students involved in the 2024 project was 42, larger than in the 2023 editons (36 partecipants).</p> <p>The total number of CFU delivered is above 100, much hiegher than in the 2023 editon (54)</p>
<p><i>Part of the Team that participated at the Italian Event at the Riccardo Paletti Circuit and car in action during the event</i></p>	

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #3	
Reference Person	Gian Luca Foresti, Luca Casarsa
Key-descriptors	
Title	AeroUD
TAGS	Air Cargo Challenge
Date	1 st October 2023 – 30 September 2024
Participants	12 Students from Mechanical and Electrical Engineering and Computer courses
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The aims of the project is to provide to the participating student the opportunity to develop a complete engineering project, with the final purpose to design, produce and test o fixed wing drone to participate at the international competition Air Cargo Challenge (ACC)</p> <p>The University of Udine has participated to ACC since 2015, competed in the 2024 edition and a new team is currently working for the 2026 competition (the ACC is held every second year and organized by the winning team of the previous edition). It sees involved about 40 teams representing universities form all over the Europe, middle east and south Americas. By their participation to the projects, the students have the opportunities to empowering their engineering skills and acquire new soft skill that will be surely useful for a faster and smoother entry into their professional life.</p> <p>The project involved a total of 12 students that during the period from October 2023 and September 2024, designed and built fixed wing drone according to the ACC2024 regulations. The students were divided in different working groups with specific tasks and accordingly with their curricula of study: Aerodynamic Department; Structural Department, Avionics and Power Train Department, Marketing Department. Each Department work was coordinated by a responsible, the overall team work was supervised by a Team Leader and a Technical Officer. A new drone was designed and built in 8 months, in order to have it ready to compete in the 2024 ACC held in Aachen in the period 9-12 July 2024.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event was promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Support documents	https://aeroud.uniud.it/ https://aachen-drone.de/ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Air_Cargo_Challenge
Notes	
CFU Delivered	<p>The number of students involved in the 2024 project was 12, larger than in the 2023 editons (6 partecipants).</p> <p>The total number of CFU delivered is above 60, hiegher than in the 2023 editon (36)</p>
Part of the Team at the ACC 2024 competition and the developed drone during a flight mission at the competition	

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #6	
Reference Person	Monica Calcagno
Key-descriptors	
Title	Artistic Management
TAGS	Innovative Education, Management, Visual, Craft, Theater
Date	February - May 2024
Participants	20
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The Artistic Management Minor includes the following specific content areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Artistic Techniques: Exploration and mastery of artistic techniques, including theatre, literature, and video production. ● Interdisciplinary Skills: Integration of creative and technical knowledge for effective management. ● Managerial Insight: Understanding the strategic role of art in leadership and decision-making. ● Innovation & Creativity: Development of innovative thinking and creative problem-solving skills. ● Narrative Development: Crafting compelling narratives for corporate communication and storytelling. ● Change Management: Learning to drive positive change within organizations through artistic approaches. <p>With teachers and students, we imagined the structure of the route that viewers would follow to discover the Squero.</p> <p>The route is supported by a free izitravel application programmed specifically by the consultant for our workshop, into which we uploaded, once the route was defined, the various contributions designed for each stage. Between each stage, the viewer is asked to solve a riddle. To solve the riddle, he or she will have to watch the video contribution to get the information needed to move on to the next stage.</p> <p>The video contributions, as will be seen from the card, are of different nature: artistic, documentary, poetic.</p> <p>A different way, from time to time, to find out more about the Squero and to integrate with the “physical” visit.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event was promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1DxHVbXIU5Tu6T4efwbe2Cc0m2i2ZEIJK
Notes	
Image from the event	

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #6	
Reference Person	Alessio Cotugno
Key-descriptors	
Title	Contamination Laboratory (CLAB): Think, design and create Ippolito Nievo's Literary Park (formerly: Revitalizing Cultural Heritage for Sustainable Tourism: The Ippolito Nievo Literary Park Design Challenge)
TAGS	#Innovative Education #Literarypark #Tourism #Culture
Date	6 th , 10 th -13 th , 16 th September 2024
Participants	4 researchers/teachers, 2 university students, 13 high school students, 1 expert in design-thinking methodologies
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>This C.Lab is grounded on these questions: "It is possible to bring the Italian literary heritage closer to a wide audience, through an emotional rather than cognitive approach that exploits the potential evocative potential of places and landscapes from which literary works have drawn inspiration?" "Is it possible to foster a process of rediscovery and enhancement, both cultural and economic, of those same territories, often marginalised with respect to the usual tourist routes?" The challenge of designing Ippolito Nievo's Literary Park has been configured as an intellectually stimulating experience of active didactics. This challenge extends an invitation to students from high schools and universities to immerse themselves in an exploration of the relationships between literature, economics, tourism and sustainability. Students are invited to take on the role of custodians of cultural heritage and designers of sustainable tourism. The lab has been an engaging educational experience that promoted critical thinking, creativity and a sense of responsibility on the local territory. Participants have been invited to draw inspiration from the literary legacy of Ippolito Nievo and other existing literary parks to conceive a literary park that not only pays homage to the writer, but also represents a sustainable cultural tourism product. This dual objective will required critical thinking, planning skills, design capacity and cultural awareness. Students, through design thinking, re-imagine a distributed cultural heritage offering cultural involvement, including not only museum-related exhibitions, but also guided tours, educational programmes and cultural events that bring literary writing. At the conclusion of the CLab the participants developed four projects for Ippolito Nievo's Literary Park that combined art, economic and social sustainability and enhancement of cultural heritage, directly connected with INEST research topics (thanks to teachers' lessons and suggestions deriving from their own research projects).</p> <p>Programme:</p> <p>DAY 0: KICKOFF DAY Friday 6 September 9:00-13:00 Presentation of the Workshop</p> <p>DAY 1: EXPLORATION (field visit) Tuesday 10 September 09:00-18:00 Exploration of Nievo's places; research phase preparatory to project ideas Physical visit to key places linked to the author, creative inspiration sessions through the reading of selected passages</p> <p>DAY 2: EXPLORATION + DEFINITION Wed 11 September 09:00-17:00 Project definition: closing of the exploration phase and start of convergence towards the project challenge, with a focus on teachers' researches: cultural heritage Accessibility, Tourist flow management/Visitor management, Authenticity VS Stereotypes</p> <p>DAY 3: DESIGN AND PROTOTYPING Thursday 12 September 09:00-17:00 Creating projects and starting convergence towards a prototype</p> <p>DAY 4: TESTING AND IMPROVEMENT Fri 13 Sep 09:00-17:00 Testing and improvement: finalisation of prototypes through testing and re-design</p> <p>DAY 5: FINAL PRESENTATIONS Mon 16 September 17:00-19:00 Council Hall of the Municipality of Portogruaro, in presence of local community Objectives: Presentations of the projects developed during the workshop and award ceremonies</p>

Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	Emails to students and to stakeholders to be involved
Website/link	

Notes

Images from the event

MISSIONE 4
ISTRUZIONE
RICERCA

Interconnected Nord-Est
Innovation Ecosystem

Cross-Cutting Activity #4

Education
& Lifelong Learning

i NEST

Annex 3

Lifelong Learning Courses

***Performed
in the frame of
Milestone #27***

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #1	
Reference Person	Daniele Morselli, Michele Cagol
Key-descriptors	
Title	University Pedagogy 1: Course Design (former title “Curriculum design for university and secondary school’s instructors”)
TAGS	#Innovative Education #Engineering #Learning Factories
Dates	17 April 2024 16 – 19 Learning in the XXIst century 24 April 2024 16 - 19 The theory of constructive alignment 8 May 2024 16 - 19 Writing intended learning outcomes 15 May 2024 16 - 19 How to shape an effective lecture? Suggestions from evidence-based research 29 May 2024 16 – 19 Integrating digital tools in the lesson to ensure participation and deep learning 11 June 2024 16 – 19 Assessment of intended learning outcomes 18 June 2024 16 – 19 Designing Scoring Rubrics
Participants	45 (15 of which received the Open Badge)
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>This course was for university instructors and secondary school teachers, but also for young researchers who want to learn the theory and practice of curriculum design. The theoretical basis was represented by the theory of constructive alignment by John Biggs et al. (2022). To promote deep learning in students, instructors and teachers become designers of learning environments, and seek to align intended learning outcomes, teaching and learning activities, and assessment.</p> <p>Through 7 meetings, the 45 initial participants learnt how to design a curriculum constructively aligned with a lot of examples and group practice. The course was given by online lessons with experts, chapters to be read at home (in the flipped classroom style) with guided written reflections, and a final project entailing a unit designed with constructive alignment. The experts were professors from Politecnico di Milano (Sancassani) and from University of Helsinki (Kinnunen and Kallunki), and also modelled good teaching by making the lessons as interactive as possible through digital tools (example Mentimeter, Forum, Socrative, Woclap, Miro etc..). During the online course (through Teams) the participants often worked in small groups through breakout rooms with digital tools such as: Padlet, Word and Power Point. All the contents were made available on a Learning Management System (Moodle). The lessons were also recorded for later use.</p> <p>3 meetings were held by the course organizers, particularly Morselli and Cagol. Two meetings were held by two Finnish experts, and two by an expert of the Polytechnic of Milan. Most of the participants were doctoral students and young researchers from the University of Bolzano, other participants came from Ca’ Foscari University of Venice. The participants who took part in at least 6 meetings, made reflections and presented the final artefact were granted with a Badge from UniBz. Eventually, 15 participants got the badge. Some participants could not fully participate for problems with the internet connection and were forced to drop the course.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The course was promoted through email invitations and advertisements on the iNEST website and social media (e.g., the news in the iNEST website: https://www.consorziointest.it/cc4-i-primi-due-corsi-training-education-alla-libera-universita-di-bolzano/).
Website/link	The link is to the Learning Management System and requires password for access MOODLE PAGE https://ole.unibz.it/course/view.php?id=11487
Images from the Event	
	The first picture shows the program as it was forwarded to colleagues at UniBz and the other participating Universities.

University Pedagogy 1: Course Design

Speakers:

Paivi Kinnunen & Veera Kallunki, University of Helsinki,
Susanna Sancassani, Politecnico di Milano
Daniele Morselli, Michele Cagol, Free University of Bolzano.

Where: Online

When:

17 April 16 - 19 Learning in university settings in the XXI century
 24 April 16 - 19 The theory of constructive alignment
 8 May 16 - 19 Writing intended learning outcomes
 15 May 16 - 19 Integrating digital tools in the lesson to ensure participation and deep learning
 29 May 16 - 19 How to shape an effective lecture? Suggestions from evidence-based research
 11 June 16 - 19 Assessment of intended learning outcomes
 18 June 16 - 19 Designing Scoring Rubrics

Language: English

Target: University professors, High school teachers, researchers (A/R, RTDs) and PhD students

Topics:

Learning in university settings in the XXI century
 The theory of constructive alignment
 Writing intended learning outcomes
 Integrating digital tools in the lesson to ensure participation and deep learning
 How to shape an effective lecture? Suggestions from evidence-based research
 Assessment of intended learning outcomes
 Designing Scoring Rubrics

Participation is mandatory. The course includes readings and written reflections, and a final project. Upon successful completion the participant will receive a badge.

[Register here!](#)

The second picture is a screenshot from the Teams system illustrating the chat with participants, some participants and the recording, hence a comprehensive learning environment completed by the LMS.

Apr 14 risposte da tu, CAVALLI Giulia (Guest), Favaretto Mattia (Student EDU 21) e altre 5 persone

CAVALLI Giulia (Guest) 15.05 17:50

I am so sorry but I am afraid I must leave a bit early today. I'll catch up with the recording. Thank you for today and see you next time!

Morselli Daniele 15.05 17:51

Very nice question Mattia, I wondered the same 🤔. In any case in his studies Hattie considered several variables including: family, student, family, school, teacher, program, and teaching mostra di più

Registrazione in corso
Morselli Daniele

2h 58m 33s

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #1	
Reference Person	Monica Parricchi
Key-descriptors	
Title	Financial education for university students and graduates: build life skills
TAGS	Money, financial education, awareness, future, mountain economic
Dates	May 9, 4:00 PM – 7:00 PM Marco Pugliese: Introduction to financial education, budget definition, introduction to ESG May 16, 3:30 PM – 7:30 PM Monica Parricchi: Education for sustainability and pedagogy May 23, 3:30 PM – 7:30 PM Monica Parricchi: The relationship between pedagogy, territory, and institutions May 27, 4:00 PM – 7:00 PM Marco Pugliese: Introduction to the economic and financial system, case studies, and simulation of sustainable startups June 20, 9:00 AM – 1:00 PM Monica Parricchi: Planning and building well-being
Participants	40
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>Financial education, the core focus of this course, aims to integrate essential knowledge on personal finance, basic economic concepts, and financial planning tools, providing participants with the skills needed to build and maintain their financial well-being and ensure long-term stability. This topic is particularly significant in a context where financial decisions increasingly impact quality of life and social well-being, especially for groups facing specific challenges, such as women, who are often involved in significant economic decisions with individual and community-level repercussions.</p> <p>The course provided practical tools and theoretical knowledge to develop essential transversal skills: from conscious management of financial resources to sustainable financial planning, and the ability to make informed and responsible decisions. Through a multidisciplinary approach, participants were guided in understanding and applying financial principles in various life stages, with a particular focus on the importance of planned strategies for achieving personal well-being and economic security.</p> <p>The educational activities combined interactive lessons, practical workshops, and guided reflection moments, ensuring participants not only master the content but also develop the ability to adapt it to their personal and professional contexts.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The course was promoted through email invitations sent within unibz as well as other iNEST Universities.
Website/link	https://llguide.unibz.it/assets/studium-generale/2024-04-09-INEST-Financial-Education-Syllabus-2023-24.pdf
Images from the Event	
	The first picture shows the program as it was forwarded to colleagues at UniBz and the other participating Universities.

Syllabus

Descrizione del corso

Titolo del corso	L'educazione finanziaria per tutti
Codice del corso	89184
Settore scientifico disciplinare del corso	SECS-P/06 ECONOMIA APPLICATA M-PED/01 PEDAGOGIA GENERALE E SOCIALE
Semestre	2
Anno del corso	2023-2024
Crediti formativi	Nessuno
Giorno e ora delle lezioni	9 maggio 16-19 16 maggio 15:30-19:30 23 maggio 15:30-19:30 27 maggio 16-19 20 giugno 09-13
Sede e/o online	Bolzano in modalità ibrida (in presenza e online)
Numero totale di ore di lezione	18
Livello (bachelor, master, per tutti)	Per tutti
Frequenza	lezioni aperte alla cittadinanza
Corsi propedeutici	nessuno

Obiettivi formativi specifici del corso

L'educazione finanziaria, al centro di questo corso, mira a combinare le finanze personali, i concetti finanziari di base e la pianificazione finanziaria, fornendo gli strumenti necessari per aiutare le persone a costruire e mantenere il benessere personale, garantendo una stabilità finanziaria di lungo termine. Questo aspetto si rivela di cruciale importanza per tutti, ma assume un'importanza ancora maggiore per le donne, che spesso si trovano ad affrontare decisioni significative a livello personale che comportano spese considerevoli con ricadute sociali diversificate rispetto agli uomini.

Gli obiettivi del corso sono trasversali e mirano a fornire ai presenti le competenze finanziarie di base necessarie per prendere decisioni informate, gestire le proprie finanze in modo efficace e pianificare un futuro finanziario sostenibile. Attraverso un approccio interdisciplinare, il corso si propone di far acquisire ai partecipanti la capacità

1/3

In the other images, multiple moments of the co-teaching sessions are depicted, including the use of materials from our economic laboratory, LABEE. In this specific case, the shared lesson integrated pedagogical and economic knowledge at both an academic and practical level.

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE 2	
Reference Persons	Anna Serbati, Federica Picasso
Key-descriptors	
Title	MOOC Le competenze valutative digitali/Technology Enhanced Assessment and Feedback skills
TAGS	#Assessment, Feedback, Technology, Digital Competencies
Date	June 2023 - still open
Participants	110 <i>Academic staff (including PhD Students, Post doc researchers and administrative staff)</i>
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>“Digital Assessment Competences” MOOC is a free and self paced online course, created for University of Trento academics in the context of a doctoral project (cycle XXXVII) with the collaboration of the company Edutech (Trento), specialised in educational technologies. The course is designed in order to foster the development of digital competences in the field of Technology Enhanced Assessment and Feedback practices with the collaboration of University of Trento Teaching and Learning Centre (FormID).</p> <p>It is divided in 6 modules: each module is organised with a video, related activities and materials and links to external resources useful for self-directed study. Furthermore, two activities are designed to scaffold reflections and the teaching planning, in the light of the content used during the online course. One-to-one coaching is also planned for university teachers interested in direct experimentation and application in class of assessment and feedback practices enhanced by the use of technology and related tools.</p> <p>Introductory Module: introduction to the course with presentation and institutional greetings.</p> <p>Module 0 - Introduction to the new DigCompEdu Educators Competences:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -0.1 The DigCompEdu - European Framework for the Digital Competence of Educators -0.2 Digital Competence, Evaluation and Feedback <p>Module 1 - The basics of instructional design</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1 The basics of instructional design - Part 1. The Expected Learning Outcomes 1.2 The Constructive Alignment 1.3 The basics of instructional design - Part 2. Instructional methodologies and architectures 1.4 The basics of instructional design - Part 3. Assessment <p>Module 2 - The different types of assessment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2.1 Summative/certificative assessment, formative assessment and diagnostic assessment 2.2 Assessment for Learning 2.3 Sustainable Assessment 2.4 Feedback 2.5 Peer review and Peer feedback <p>Module 3 - Assessment and Technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.1 Technology Enhanced Assessment: the principles 3.2 The value and potential of technology in assessment design (JISC, 2010) 3.3 Technology Enhanced Assessment systems and the connection with teachers' digital competences 3.4 Design examples with Technology Enhanced Assessment (JISC, 2010) <p>Module 4 - Tools for Implementing Technology Enhanced Assessment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Feedback 2. Quiz 3. Diary 4. Workshop 5. Task

	6. Wooclap
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event was promoted internally at the University of Trento through email invitations and advertisements on social media channels.
Website/link	https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/digcompedu_en
Notes	
Description of eventual requirements	The Massive Open Online Course is devoted to Italian academics in charge of teaching. A minimum of teaching experience is suggested to attend the course for the best learning experience, considering that the course scaffolds reflection on prior experiences.

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #3	
Reference Person	Gian Luca Foresti
Key-descriptors	
Title	AI-based approaches for Anomaly Detection in Industrial Plants
TAGS	AI for Anomaly Detection
Date	July 1-5, 2024
Participants	About 20 PhD Students from University College London UCL (UK), Centrale Méditerranée (FR), Università di Bologna (IT), Ecole normale supérieure (FR), Kaunas University of Technology KTU (LT), Università degli Studi di Udine (IT), Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II (IT), Politecnico di Milano (IT), Institut polytechnique Paris (FR), Università della Tuscia (IT). About 10 Business Participants from local companies (Danieli Automation, Electrolux Group, Eurosystem Spa, FEC Italia Srl, Procne Srl, Progetto Nachste Srl, RDV Network Srl, Sacer-Uliana Luciano Srl, Time Srl, Video Systems).
Details	
Description of event	<p>"AI-DLDA: International Summer School on Artificial Intelligence", the AI PhD summer school, organized by the Department of Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics (DMIF) of the University of Udine. Artificial intelligence applied to the sectors of Medical Image Analysis, Cyber Security and Computer Vision (Machine learning & Deep networks, mathematical image analysis) are the focuses of the summer school which has been taken place in the spaces of the New Rizzi Library at Udine. An opportunity for all participants to interact with researchers from all over the world, and to create networking opportunities with professionals in the AI sector. The morning plenary sessions, held by internationally renowned speakers, are followed by practical afternoon workshops.</p> <p>The AI School has been carried out in presence (only few lectures have been carried out on-line) and it has been organized into Lecturers during the morning, held by internationally renowned speakers, and practical afternoon workshops and Lab activities.</p> <p><u>Lectures</u></p> <p>Sebastiano Battiato, Università di Catania "Generative AI and Impostor Bias: Advances, Challenges, and Future Directions"</p> <p>Emanuele Rodolà, Università Sapienza di Roma "Unlocking Neural Composition"</p> <p>Lamberto Ballan, Università di Padova, "From context-aware motion prediction to embodied visual navigation"</p> <p>Stefano Zanero, Politecnico di Milano, "A tormented love story: AI and Cybersecurity"</p> <p>Andreas Windisch, JOANNEUM RESEARCH "Rise of the Machines: AI's New Dawn"</p> <p>Gustavo Carneiro, University of Surrey, "Learning to Complement and to Defer to Multiple Users using Personalized Human-AI Collaborative Classifiers"</p> <p><u>Workshop</u></p> <p>Jarod Zheng and Gong Yan, Lenovo, "Digital & Intelligent Transformation solutions for Portfolio & Product Planning PPM"</p> <p>Lorenzo Baraldi, Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia, "An introduction to the use of PyTorch and Google Colab Environments"</p> <p>Nicola Demo, SISSA, "Deep Learning Approaches for Solving Differential Equations: Physics-Informed Neural Network and Neural Operator"</p> <p>Andreas Windisch and Michael Somma, JOANNEUM RESEARCH, "Deep reinforcement learning"</p> <p>Giuseppe Serra and Alex Falcon, Università di Udine, "Text-to-Metaverse Retrieval: A New Frontier in Search"</p> <p>Zaira Manigrasso, Università di Udine, "AI-driven material characterization"</p> <p>Axel De Nardin, Università di Udine, "Document Analysis and Understanding in the Era of Deep Learning"</p>

	<p>Kevin Roitero, Università di Udine, “Practical Applications of Large Language Models with PyTorch and Hugging Face”</p> <p>Daniele Fornasier, Beantech, “Pervasive AI for manufacturing: from advanced automation applications to intelligent ecosystem monitoring”</p> <p>Federico Cussigh, R-Tree Technologies, “Generative AI & Knowledge management”</p> <p>Dante Degl’Innocenti and Marco Pavan, Datamantix, “Real-World Applications of Deep Learning and Machine Learning in Industry and Medicine”</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event was promoted internally at the University of Trento through email invitations and advertisements on social media channels.
Website/link	https://www.aidlda.it/

Notes

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE 9	
Reference Persons	Andrea Cangiani, Stefano Salon, Alberto Maspero
Lifelong learning Course Key-descriptors	
Title	Digital twins for sustainable economy
TAGS	Digital twin, data-driven modelling, data analytics, artificial intelligence, edge computing, physics-based modelling, physics-based machine learning, system modelling, model order reduction
Date	September-November 2024
Participants	R&D personnel from several companies
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>Lifelong learning course targeted to R&D specialists held between 30th September – 4th November 2024 through 5 full afternoon sessions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction to Digital Twins and Physical Modeling 2. Data-Driven Modeling for Digital Twins: Simulation and AI 3. Case Studies of Industrial Digital Twins 4. Digital Twins of Marine Environments 5. Round table; presentations by start-up SINDREL and TRANSPOBANK <p>Sessions 1-4 were held at the Camera di Commercio Venezia Giulia Trieste Gorizia (Trieste) and were lectured in turns by the teams of the four nodes of Spoke 9 (SISSA, UNITS, UNIPD, OGS) thus leveraging the combine expertise available within the Spoke. The final session at SISSA was led by all four teams and was enhanced by presentations by the CC1 1st cycle acceleration Demo Day start-up SINDREL and winner of iNEST Bando a Cascata TRANSPOBANK (attending the course).</p> <p>Close to thirty participants from seven companies attended the sessions. An iNEST attendance certificate was awarded to participants engaging in the course.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	<p>The course was advertised through the Spoke 9 dedicated webpage linked to the iNEST site. Moreover, given that the event was organized with the collaboration of the Camera di Commercio Venezia Giulia Trieste Gorizia, the event was also advertised in the Camera di Commercio's website.</p> <p>The lectures were organized in hybrid mode using the Zoom platform and were indeed also attended by members of the iNEST consortium from other spokes.</p> <p>All of the course material has been made available through a dedicated github repository available to the participants and to all members of iNEST upon request.</p>
Website/link	https://inest.spoke9.sissa.it/digital-twins-for-a-sustainable-economy/
Notes	
Remark	Included in the Report, even if formally started during Milestone #27

Image(s) from the event

Questo corso offre una comprensione approfondita dei **gemelli digitali** (DT), coprendo le basi teoriche, i casi di studio e le applicazioni pratiche. I partecipanti acquisiranno conoscenze preziose da applicare in contesti reali, per un futuro industriale sostenibile.

Informazioni chiave

Quando
30 settembre – 4 novembre 2024

Dove
Sessioni 1-4: CCIAA Venezia Giulia Trieste Gorizia (Trieste, piazza della Borsa n°14)
Sessione 5: SISSA (Trieste, via Bonomea n°265)

Ore del corso
20 ore

Lingua
Italiano

Costo
€200 per azienda

Per iscriversi:

Orari
Sessioni: 13:30 – 18:00 (con coffee break di 30 min)
Light Lunch: 12:30 – 13:30 (prima delle sessioni 1 e 5)

Modalità di partecipazione
Sessioni 1, 5: solo in presenza
Sessioni 2, 3, 4: in presenza/online

Spoke Leader

Affiliates

Digital Twin per l'Economia Sostenibile

CC4

4023
Life Long Learning

Cross-Cutting Activity 4 – Education,
from ITS to Lifelong Learning

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE 9	
Reference Persons	Antonia Larese, Mario Putti
Lifelong learning Course Key-descriptors	
Title	Mixed and stabilised finite element methods
TAGS	Physics-based modelling, high fidelity modeling, CFD, stabilization techniques
Date	6-28 November 2023
Participants	15
Details	
Description of event and programme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to mixed methods. Some examples: Darcy’s problem, Stokes’ problem, Maxwell’s problem, Elasticity, Reissner-Mindlin plates. Finite element approximation. Matrix structure. • Finite element approximation of mixed problems: general theory. Babuska-Lax-Milgram’s theorem. Generalised Cea’s lemma. Ladyzhenskaya-Babu ´ ska-Brezzi’s theorem. de Rham’s complex. • Stabilised finite element methods. Basic concept. The variational multi-scale approach. Application to mixed problems. • Darcy’s problem. Primal form, dual form. Inf-sup conditions and examples of compatible approximations. Stabilised finite element approximation. • Stokes’ problem. Two-field formulation. Three-field formulation. Inf-sup conditions and examples of compatible approximations. Stabilised finite element approximation. • Maxwell’s problem. Kikuchi formulation. An example of inf-sup stable approximation. Augmented stabilised finite element approximation. • Elasticity. Stress-displacement formulation. Stress-strain-displacement formulation. Infsup conditions. Stabilised finite element approximation. • Reissner-Mindlin plates. Derivation of the problem. Inf-sup conditions and examples of compatible approximations. Stabilised finite element approximation. • Introduction to hybrid methods. Hybridisation of Poisson’s problem. Inf-sup conditions. Stabilised finite element approximation
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	Web site, emails
Website/link	https://stem.elearning.unipd.it/user/index.php?id=7768
Notes	

MISSIONE 4
ISTRUZIONE
RICERCA

Interconnected Nord-Est
Innovation Ecosystem

Cross-Cutting Activity #4

Education
& Lifelong Learning

i NEST

Annex 4

***Innovative
Education
Initiatives
& Pilot-Projects***

***Scheduled
for
Milestone #28***

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #1	
Reference Persons	Margherita Molinaro, Erwin Rauch
Key-descriptors	
Title	Special track on “Innovative Engineering Education” at the 3rd ISIEA Conference
TAGS	#Innovative Education #Engineering #Learning Factories
Duration	Half day
Date	June 2025
Details	
Background	The <i>International Symposium on Industrial Engineering and Automation</i> (ISIEA) has been launched in 2022 as a new initiative of the Industrial Engineering and Automation macro-area of the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano. It is an international scientific conference (with proceedings published in September as a volume of Springer’s Lecture Notes) dealing with different Engineering topics. The topic of the 2025 edition will be Latest Advancements In Mechanical Engineering. We plan to organize a new special track within the conference focused on “Innovative Engineering Education”.
Description of initiative/project	A special track/session will be organized within the 3 rd ISIEA Conference dealing with tools, methods, and formats for Engineering Education. This will offer a platform also to iNEST staff to exchange best practices and experiences to strengthen the higher education teaching offer in the Engineering field. Examples of topics that will be included in the track are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New (digital) tools for Engineering Educations; - The role of Learning Factories in Engineering Education; - Serious Games for Engineering Education; - Problem-Based Learning in Engineering Education; - Engineering Curricula Design; - Integrating Digitalization and Sustainability in Engineering Education; - Life-Long Learning in the Engineering field.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	iNEST professors and researchers (in particular in the Engineering field) belonging to all the Spokes will be invited to present a paper or attend the special track on Innovative Engineering Education.
References	Conference website: https://isiea.events.unibz.it/
Status	
Scheduled in 2025	

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #2	
Reference Person	Roberta Cuel
Key-descriptors	
Title	Theatrical Improvisation Workshop for high school teachers
TAGS	Extract keywords by the project: Theatrical improvisation, Team building, Trust in teams, Listening Acceptance of the proposal, Lateral thinking, Communication management
Duration	The laboratory consists of 4 lessons of 3 hours, for 12 hours. We plan to conduct this activity in different high schools and university courses for three years.
Date	February-March 2025
Details	
Description of initiative/project	<p>The course encourages acquiring skills and tools for group work, negotiation, and team collaboration.</p> <p>Theatrical improvisation is very effective for developing a range of basic emotional, relational, and cognitive skills that allow people to acquire versatile and positive behavior helpful in working in groups, such as being able to listen empathically to other members of the group, promote creative and adaptive capacity in solving problems, learn to accept the proposal and think divergently, improve the management of individual decisions, increase the ability to stay focused on objectives and acquire tools for conflict management.</p> <p>From a social point of view, collaboration skills are developed, social stereotypes are eliminated, and awareness of the value of each individual in their peculiarities is created. Consequently, acceptance and integration are achieved among all class group members. The lessons are divided into two parts. The first part includes exercises focused on bodily expressiveness, movement, facial and vocal expressiveness, and group dynamics. The second part focuses on verbal expressiveness and allows participants to experiment with jokes and practice their expressive potential in a welcoming environment that encourages creativity and emotional expression. The proposed exercises promote body awareness, emotional awareness, and active listening to others.</p> <p>Lesson 1: Public speaking and effective communication.- This initial journey focuses on bodily expressiveness and vocal techniques to develop effective communication and public speaking skills. The goal is to create a trusting and dynamic group environment where everyone can feel comfortable expressing themselves creatively.</p> <p>Lesson 2: Improvisation tools as resources for teachers.- This part of the lessons offers improvisation tools that can be used as resources for teachers to manage eye contact, active listening, and creativity in finding innovative solutions.</p> <p>Lesson 3: The relationship between the education and education sector.- Theoretical studies on knowledge sharing, group management, confrontation, and conflict management are explored to deepen the understanding of the relationship between education and the education sector. Through theories and experiential exercises, the theme of the effects of improvisation in work groups (such as class councils) and the management of confrontation and conflict between colleagues will be explored.</p> <p>Lesson 4: Dealing with others.-This final part of the lessons includes a series of exercises to put the tools learned in previous meetings into practice and to effectively approach relationships.</p> <p>Alongside the technical-expressive methodologies, reflection-sharing methodologies are also used to help participants reflect on the challenges of communicating clearly and personally while understanding the importance of welcoming listening.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Criteria for Participation	
Requirements	<i>The course will initially be aimed at high school teachers and students of some university courses; then, it will be extended to other schools that request it.</i>

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #4	
Reference Person	Massimiliano Condotta
Key-descriptors	
Title	Wooden construction Live Workshop
TAGS	Workshop, practical experience, wood, Venice
Duration	40 hours in total, 20 hours lectures and 20 hours practical activities with teachers
Participants	IUAV students
Details	
Description of initiative/project	<p>The proposed course is configured as an experimental method of teaching in architecture in which the notions learned in frontal lectures are subsequently enhanced in practical experience.</p> <p>The main area of reference is wooden constructions.</p> <p>The objective of the workshop is to provide students with technical skills on wooden constructions that include both compositional and construction principles.</p> <p>The aim is to train future architects who know how to consciously design wooden structures, being able to appropriately exploit the potential of the material, especially in relation to its environmental sustainability.</p> <p>The structure of the workshop is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A first part where students will follow ex-cathedra lectures at university; - A second part where student will design a wooden structure; - A third part where students will construct, with the support of a company, the design structure. <p>The object of the workshop is the design of docking structures and/or information pavilions on the Certosa island in Venice.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The workshop focuses on sustainability in the construction sector. The practical experience is localized in the city of Venice that is the main pilot of the iNest Spoke 4. Innovative solutions and materials will be tested in the practical experience.
Website/link	Oppenheimer, Andrea; Hursley, Timothy (2002). <i>Rural Studio: Samuel Mockbee and the Architecture of Decency</i> . Princeton Architectural Press. http://ruralstudio.org
Notes	
Revisiting of the Topic	During the initial planning stages, we faced some challenges regarding safety requirements for a workshop on wooden construction, which was originally intended to be mostly a hands-on, practical course. As a result, we were unable to launch the workshop as planned. However, given the significance of wooden construction in promoting sustainability in the building sector, we are committed to revisiting this topic. Our intention is to transform it into a more comprehensive program, potentially developing it into a master's course to deepen participants' expertise in sustainable construction practices (<u>see Table below</u>)

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #4	
Reference Person	Massimiliano Condotta
Key-descriptors	
Title	Wooden construction Master
TAGS	Master, practical experience, wood, Venice
Duration	
Participants	
Details	
Background	Adequate skills in architecture are required.
Description of initiative/project	<p>The proposed Master is configured as an experimental course of teaching in architecture in which the notions learned in frontal lectures are subsequently enhanced in practical experience.</p> <p>The main area of reference is wooden constructions.</p> <p>The objective of the Master is to provide students with technical skills on wooden constructions that include both compositional and construction principles.</p> <p>The aim is to train future architects who know how to consciously design wooden structures, being able to appropriately exploit the potential of the material, especially in relation to its environmental sustainability.</p> <p>The structure of the Master is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A first part where students will follow ex-cathedra lectures at university; • A second part where student will design a wooden structure;
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The Master focuses on sustainability in the construction sector. The practical experience is localized in the city of Venice that is the main pilot of the iNest Spoke 4. Innovative solutions and materials will be tested in the practical experience.
References	Oppenheimer, Andrea; Hursley, Timothy (2002). <i>Rural Studio: Samuel Mockbee and the Architecture of Decency</i> . Princeton Architectural Press. http://ruralstudio.org
Notes	
Requirements	The Master is aimed with a degree in Architecture or Engineer.
Revisiting of the Topic	A wooden construction workshop was initially designed as a hands-on course. However, due to safety concerns and in order to explore the critical topic of timber construction in greater depth, we have decided to transform it into a master's program. This new format will allow us to address the subject more comprehensively, emphasizing the importance of sustainable practices in the construction industry while ensuring a safer learning environment for participants.

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #4	
Reference Person	Massimiliano Condotta and other supervisors, based on the RTs.
Key-descriptors	
Title	Spoke 4 workshop series on Research Topics
TAGS	Hands-on workshops, students meet research topics, professionals
Duration	1 intensive week in September 2025
Participants	luav students, professionals (e.g. architects, designers, urban planners), supervisors
Details	
Description of event and programme	The workshop cycle will consist of 4-5 parallel workshops, each focusing on a different theme derived from the research topics of spoke 4. These workshops will take place in September during an intensive one-week session and will grant 4 CFU (credits) of type D to students who complete the required hours. A key feature of this initiative is the collaboration between students, researchers, and professionals in design teams. This fosters cross-disciplinary knowledge exchange and creates a unique opportunity for students to gain practical experience while working on real-world projects. The workshops aim to bridge the gap between academia, research, and the professional field, enhancing the learning experience and preparing students for future challenges in their careers. The initiative also encourages innovative thinking, with each workshop addressing pressing issues such as sustainability, energy transition, and urban planning in line with current global needs.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	A key element is the constructive exchange and sharing of knowledge that will occur in the team work involving students, researchers, and professionals.
Website/link	
Notes	
Requirements	Some workshops are reserved for architecture students, others for urban planning, with a further distinction between bachelor's and master's degree programs.
Upgrade	A new element compared to the 2024 workshop format (23rd - 27th September 2024) will be the involvement of architects and professionals in the field of construction, working alongside student teams to foster knowledge exchange and collaboration between university, research, and professionals.

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #4	
Reference Person	Massimiliano Condotta, Rosaria Revellini, Valeria Tatano, Elisa Zatta
Key-descriptors	
Title	Study Day on New Materials for sustainable constructions
TAGS	Innovation, university, research, territory
Duration	One day event
Participants	Professionals, professors, researchers
Details	
Description of event and programme	In April 2025, a series of iNEST seminars will be held at Ca' Tron, Venice, focusing on the themes of Spoke 4 - City, Architecture, and Sustainable Design. Specifically, the conference will center on New Materials, aiming to share research with local companies and foster synergies between universities and local communities under the banner of innovation. The event will have an educational value for the professionals and all the participants, who will gain insights into the outcomes of research activities and the innovation tools available to SMEs and bigger companies.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	In the morning, an overview of the contributions produced during the research activities at luav will be presented, while the afternoon will feature a series of talks on innovative and sustainable materials, followed by an active discussion on innovation tools for businesses, including grants and research projects.
Website/link	
Notes	
Requirements	None
Note	This sharing event was not initially planned, but we identified the need for collaboration and knowledge exchange, so the goal of the day is to create a moment for collaboration between universities, businesses, and local communities by presenting the outcomes of research activities on innovative and sustainable materials. The event aims to foster knowledge transfer, encourage synergies, and provide useful tools for business innovation, promoting active dialogue between academia and the industrial sector.

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Stefano Ghidoni
Key-descriptors	
Title	Virtualization of Laboratories: The T.2020 Project
TAGS	ICT Lab, Virtual labs, BYOD
Date	Spring 2025
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The T.2020 System (known also as VLAB), as the result of the work of a special commission of the School of Engineering formed in 2017, includes a systemic “vision” on IT services for teaching aimed at creating a perfect match between the needs of teachers and the tools available of the students.</p> <p>The study considered the IT tools for teaching – digital learning – (initially for Engineering teaching) and set the following objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • classrooms designed for teaching that combines the traditional frontal method in the classroom with activities mediated by computers or mobile systems (teaching blended), including modalities in which (1) the lesson becomes homework, while the time in the classroom is used for collaborative activities , experiences, debates and workshops (Flipped Classroom) and (2) active learning moments are incorporated to make training more engaging and akin to the needs of future professionals (Active Learning); • didactic structures that adopt criteria to facilitate inclusion , in order to favor the improvement of university life of all female students and all students and to reduce drop-out; • tools aimed at increasing the effectiveness of the teaching action, in relation to the number of students / year expected.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	Seminars on the T.2020 system will be organized by the T.2020 Commission of the School of Engineering of Padova University. Pilot sessions for professors and students of iNEST Universities will be made available.
Website/link	https://vlab.unipd.it/en/home-english/
Notes	

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Marina De Rossi
Key-descriptors	
Title	Teaching4Learning: iNEST Conference session
TAGS	Higher Education System, Active learning, Quality & Innovation in Education
Duration	First Semester 2025
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The International Innovative Teaching Conference, organized by T4L Project of UNIPD, supports a comprehensive change in university education. Learner-centered approaches are requested, implemented in integrated environments for the development of meaningful learning and lifelong skills needed for professions and life. After the pandemic emergency, which highlighted critical issues but also the potential of digital integration, the university education system is now called to re-define its identity and the adequacy of its educational mission, to offer strategic solutions at the curricular, design, methodological- technological, and organizational levels.</p> <p>The Conference intends to provide an opportunity to exchange and share reflections and experiences on some thematics that will be the basis of the working sessions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) theoretical lines and models for implementing the culture of quality in university education, considering people, environments, and teaching at the center of transformative processes; b) educational research and the use of data as a contribution and support for change; c) didactic planning underlying curricular and teaching innovation of Study Courses through the involvement and co-responsibility of all members of the university community also within an international perspective in the framework of the ARQUS alliance for innovative teaching; d) organizational and management models of structures/centers for methodological- technological innovation in teaching and the new profiles of professional skills in a faculty development perspective; e) design and re-design of support spaces, tools, and resources to enable the implementation of integrated learning environments aimed at developing multimedia and multimodal teaching processes
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The participation to T4L Conference of the Education Working Group of iNEST will be promoted in 2024 as well the organization of a Session in 2025, to share challenges and best practice of iNEST Universities and enlarge T4L Community
Website/link	https://www.unipd.it/en/t4l-project
Criteria for Participation	
Requirements	No specific requirements

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Luigi Salmaso, Elena Barsizza
Key-descriptors	
Title	Mapping gender equality in Ecosystem
TAGS	Gender equality, STEM
Duration	12 months, starting on October 1 st , 2024
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>Monitoring and analysis of the university community's has made it possible to identify three critical points on which to focus political and financial commitment to equality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the start of university careers, with female students accounting for a significantly higher proportion of students in the humanities and health-related areas, and male students in STEM sectors (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics); • the start of an academic career with the transition from post-doc to RTDa (type "a" fixed-term researcher) and RTDb (type "b" fixed-term researcher), where the paths of women and men diverge further in favour of the latter; • top positions in academic careers, where the incidence of women is significantly lower than that of men, particularly in some subject areas. <p>iNEST Universities, in the recent years, developed their Gender Equality Plan. The activity is focused, by means of a Research Grant, to elaborate the Gender Equality mapping at Ecosystem level. Activity will be performed in cooperation with Elena Cornaro Centre of Padova University, a structure that promotes teaching and training activities related to gender knowledge.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The activity of the Research Grant will be carried out by directly involving Gender Equality offices of Partner Universities, by means of a properly elaborated questionnaire.
References	Padova University, Gender Equality Plan 2022-2024
Notes	
Research Grant	The research grant has been already assigned to dr. Elema Barsizza, who started her activity in October 2024.

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #6	
Reference Person	Anna Comacchio
Key-descriptors	
Title	The Art of Management: Unleashing Creativity and Culture in the iNest ecosystem
TAGS	
Duration	2 days, to be held in 2025
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>An innovative educational event organized at the Venice School of Management that explores how the worlds of art, creativity, and culture intersect with the business world. "The Art of Management" will be a dynamic and insightful seminar designed for business professionals, managers, and entrepreneurs who want to harness the power of the arts to drive innovation, enhance leadership skills, and enrich organizational culture. Renowned experts in management, art, and culture will deliver engaging presentations and lead discussions. Participants will have the opportunity to participate in hands-on activities and workshops that stimulate creativity, enhance cultural awareness, and connect with like-minded professionals, artists, and educators in a vibrant and inspiring setting. An art exhibition, which showcases works that highlight the intersection of art, culture, and business.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Art and Business Synergy: Discovery of how art and business can mutually benefit each other, with insights into how art can inspire creativity, problem-solving, and innovation in management practices. • Leadership through Cultural Expression: Exploration of how effective leadership can be enhanced by understanding and incorporating various cultural perspectives and expressions, fostering a more inclusive and diverse workplace. • The Creative Mindset: Learning of how to cultivate a creative mindset among your teams and use artistic techniques to encourage out-of-the-box thinking in business strategy. • Art as a Source of Inspiration: Understanding how exposure to art and cultural experiences can serve as a wellspring of inspiration for decision-makers, helping them make informed and visionary choices. • Case Studies and Success Stories: insights from successful companies that have integrated art and culture into their management strategies and learn from their experiences.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #6	
Reference Person	Fabrizio Panozzo
INITIATIVE/PILOT PROJECT Key-descriptors	
Title	Summer School on Arts and Artistic Languages as Research Methodology in the Social Sciences
TAGS	
Duration	4 days, to be held in 2025
Details	
Description of event and programme	At the heart of our summer school, the critical studies approach serves as a foundational principle, guiding participants in reimagining the boundaries of research in the social sciences. The school will foster an environment that encourages students to question prevailing power dynamics, both within the arts and within society. This approach prompts them to scrutinize how art can be a potent tool for critiquing and subverting established norms and structures, challenging the status quo to illuminate underlying issues of inequality, discrimination, and injustice. The program also promotes decolonizing perspectives within research. By dismantling colonial legacies in both the arts and social sciences, we aim to foster a more inclusive, equitable, and culturally sensitive approach to knowledge production. This perspective recognizes that traditional paradigms have often marginalized voices and experiences from non-Western cultures, and we actively seek to rectify this imbalance. As students delve into the complexities of using art as a research methodology, they are encouraged to navigate sensitive subjects with care and empathy, ensuring their research respects the dignity and agency of individuals and communities involved. Participants are guided to formulate research questions that challenge conventional paradigms, question assumptions, and seek alternative interpretations. This enables them to contribute to a more nuanced and comprehensive understanding of the issues they investigate.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	Sharing objectives and results within the multifaceted iNEST ecosystem involves strategies such as publishing research proposals, policy briefs, and industry showcases; engaging with media outlets and communication channels for wider dissemination; and fostering international partnerships and exchange programs. Additionally, the use of the centralized online platform is proposed to serve as a hub for knowledge-sharing and collaboration across the ecosystem, further promoting innovation and positive societal impact.
Website/link	
Notes	

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #7	
Reference Person	Elena Claire Ricci
Key-descriptors	
Title	Risk management and innovation in agriculture
TAGS	risk management, innovation, agriculture, entrepreneurship, EntreComp, risk&law, trainingriskmanagement
Date	May – October 2025
Participants	Farmers or Future Farmers; Farming Professionals; Students; Entrepreneurs or Future Entrepreneurs; Insurers or Future Insurers
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>In agriculture there are still large knowledge gaps in terms of agricultural risk management. Farmers often lack knowledge about effective ways to protect themselves from the continuously evolving risks that they are facing. Insurance operators and other professionals often lack the technical skills to develop adequate tools tailored for agri-food-related firms. The course aims at increasing the knowledge of farmers and professionals about the assessment of the multi-facet risks that they face and will continuously face in the future. The course will also aim to improve their knowledge and understanding of the available tools so that they can more effectively evaluate how they work and if they fit their actual needs. Entrepreneurial competence will be fostered, particularly the ability to cope with uncertainty, ambiguity, and risk, that is essential to making informed decisions. Attention will be given to private and public insurance-related and risk-protection tools, but also to innovation strategies in the light of sustainable development to mitigate or adapt to such risks. The course also aims at increasing the knowledge of professionals that develop/market risk management tools about the specificities of the risks in agriculture, so that they can develop and promote effective options for the agri-food sector. Consistent with the objectives of the course, innovation will be a key driver that will also characterize the teaching aspects. Most relevant topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction to risk management - Introduction to the various types of risks that can arise with discussion of examples - Climate change risks in agriculture - What are the new challenges for agriculture given a changing climate? A discussion of changing conditions, with a particular focus on plant development and defense - Innovation for risk mitigation and adaptation - What are the innovations available for climate change mitigation and adaption to a changing situation in agriculture - Insurance and other risk management tools - Legal aspects of risk management - News from the case law of merit and the Supreme Court on the legal relevance of the adoption of appropriate organizational models also for the purposes of directors' liability. In addition, on the legislative level, the “corrective” to the Crisis Code (Legislative Decree 14/2019) came into force where further guidance on the duties and role of the administrative and supervisory body. Finally, Legislative Decree 125/2024 was adopted, which transposes the CSRD directive on sustainability reporting - Entrepreneurial Competences: to act upon opportunities and ideas, and to transform them into values for others; based on the abilities as creativity, critical thinking and problem solving, taking initiative and perseverance. - Case studies
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #7	
Reference Person	Elena Claire Ricci
Key-descriptors	
Title	What can I do for Climate Change? Evaluating choices in the agrifood domain to build stakeholder agency
TAGS	#climate change #agri-food #active citizenship #agency #consumer choices #entrepreneurship #EntreComp #sustainability&EUlegalframework #criticalthinking
Duration	February – July 2025
Participants	Citizens; Students; Young (but not only) Entrepreneurs; Young (but not only) professionals
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>Individual food-related choices and behaviours are crucial for addressing current societal challenges like climate change. The agri-food system, in particular, has strong connections to all the dimensions of sustainability and different organizational forms of this system can have very different multi-dimensional impacts. Thus, it is important to build citizen/consumer engagement on these topics to promote more conscious choices.</p> <p>The main aim is to foster agency and deliberation in societally relevant choices, like those related to climate change. The idea is to engage with individuals considering their three-facet roles as citizens, consumers, and (present or future) professionals. Indeed, in all three of these roles they make decisions that can make a difference and become agents of transformational change. The course aims at building individual knowledge about climate change and the differential climate change impacts of different food products, production processes, organizational models, etc. This will promote a critical understanding of the information and claims reported on food labels and on other available sources of information and foster agency. This can also favor the appreciation of actual Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) efforts and Sustainable Business models by firms as opposed to green washing strategies.</p> <p>Attention will be paid to entrepreneurial competence, in particular the ability of recognizing ethical principles and challenges of sustainable development.</p> <p>Consistent with the objectives of the course, innovation will be a key driver that will also characterize the teaching aspects.</p> <p>List of most relevant topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction to climate change - CSR and business in the EU legal framework - Approval of two important directives: DIRECTIVE (EU) 2024/1760 of 13 June 2024, on corporate sustainability due diligence and amending Directive (EU) 2019/1937 and Regulation (EU) 2023/2859, nonché Directive 2024/825, of 28 February 2024, amending Directives 2005/29/EC and 2011/83/EU as regards empowering consumers for the green transition through better protection against unfair practices and through better information - Sustainability issues of the food system - Entrepreneurial Competences - To reflect on the competences related: to act upon opportunities and ideas, and to transform them into values for others; based on the abilities as creativity, critical thinking and problem solving, taking initiative and perseverance - Information and mis-information - The role of citizens, consumers, and professionals in promoting more climate friendly practices - The role of new media in the way in which climate scientists can effectively give meaning to their role as science communicator.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	

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Cross-Cutting Activity #4

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Annex 5

Minors & Challenges

***Scheduled
for
Milestone #28***

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #1	
Reference Persons	Guido Orzes, Daniele Morselli
Key-descriptors	
Title	Mountain Innovation Challenge
TAGS	Design Thinking, Problem Based Learning, Challenge
Duration	3 days (around 20 hours of activities)
Details	
Background	<p>In February 2022, the Free University of Bolzano and the NOI Techpark of Bolzano designed and offered an extra-curricular programme for bachelors and masters students entitled “Students & Company Sprint”. Three companies presented an innovation challenge that student teams had to solve, mentored by experts and scientists (following the Google Desing Sprint Methodology). The programme will be re-organized in 2024-2026 thanks to financing from the European Social Fund.</p> <p>Within the iNEST project, the idea is to design a similar challenge but with some peculiarities: (1) the topic will be innovation for mountain areas; (2) the challenges will be proposed by the Spoke 1 of the iNEST consortium rather than by companies; (3) it will be addressed to students from different universities; (4) it will be organized in a weekend formula (3 days).</p>
Description of initiative/project	<p>The Mountain Innovation Challenge is an extra-curricular programme for bachelors and masters students of the Universities of the iNEST consortium. Students will be divided into interdisciplinary and inter-university groups and work on the solutions of some key challenges on the macro-topic of innovations in mountain areas. They will be coached and mentored by experts of design thinking as well as by thematic experts (professors and researches of the iNEST consortium).</p> <p>The Challenge will be organized at the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano or at a technology park in the region and will last three days (Friday to Sunday).</p> <p>Previous research show that such a programme can have very positive effects on students’ entrepreneurial competences (in particular on the ability to “work with others”), which are crucial for their employability. These effects will be evaluated based on standardized approaches (such as the EntreComp framework). Furthermore, the solutions proposed can then provide a set of interesting ideas that could be exploited by the students themselves or by different actors of the iNEST ecosystem.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The call for students will be spread to students of the 9 universities of the iNEST consortium. The goal/target is to have around 20 students from different universities of the consortium.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://heinnovate.eu/en/heinnovate-resources/resources/students-company-sprint-extra-curricular-entrepreneurial-week • Morselli, D., & Orzes, G. (2023). Evaluating an interfaculty entrepreneurship program based on challenge-based learning through the EntreComp framework. The International Journal of Management Education, 21(3), 100869.
Status	
Scheduled in 2025	

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives

SPOKE #2	
Reference Persons	Ilaria Pertot (UNITN), Milena Bigatto (HIT), Adolfo Villafiorita (Shair.Tech Srl)
Key-descriptors	
Title	Reduce the waste of food served and not eaten in canteens
TAGS	Food, waste, circular economy, consumer
Date	Scheduled 1st semester 2025
Participants	
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The waste that occurs in canteens is composed by food cooked and not served (potentially reusable) and food cooked, served and not eaten (not reusable for human consumption). There are many reasons for the second category of food waste: behavioral reasons (e.g.: lack of hunger at lunchtime due to the consumption of excessive snacks; refusal to try lesser-known dishes), plates too full of food, wrong portioning and preparing the dish, insufficient time to consume the meal (e.g.: lunch over multiple shifts), etc.</p> <p>The objective of the challenge is to identify new technological and/or educational solutions to reduce the waste of food served and not eaten.</p> <p>Background knowledge: functioning of canteens, legislation, food logistics.</p> <p>Abilities: understanding complex systems (food production, consumption, waste), identifying solutions to a problem by considering various point of view and possible actions, work in a team, prototyping solutions, preparing.</p> <p>The challenge is composed by online meetings and face-to-face activities. In addition, a visit to a canteen in Trento (Risto 3) is foreseen.</p> <p>The challenge is divided in the following steps with the related methodology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Launch of the challenge (meeting with the challenge provider - Shair.Tech Srl) ● Background acquisition (logistics, estimation of food waste, function of a canteen, related legislation, existing mitigation actions, etc.) ● Brainstorming ● Identification of solutions and refinement ● Prototyping the solution ● Testing with end-users and final refinement ● Preparation of the pitch and showcase of the solution. <p>Preparation and submission of the feasibility report</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	https://www.fao.org/nutrition/capacity-development/food-loss-and-waste/en/ https://shair.tech/ https://www.sprecozero.it/
Notes	
Description of eventual requirements	The challenge is suitable for students with background in information technology, engineering, food technologies, socio-economics, psychology, biology, agricultural sciences

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #2	
Reference Persons	Eugenio Aprea, Simone Cerroni, Flavia Gasperi, Ilaria Pertot (UNITN)
Key-descriptors	
Title	Increase the consumption of Mopur (kind of vegetarian meat)
TAGS	Veg, sustainability, vegetable proteins
Date	11-15 November 2024
Participants	
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The consumption of meat is associate to high footprint and carbon emissions. Alternatives to meat are receiving increasing attention by the food industries and the consumers. Mopur is a combination of gluten and legumes fermented with <i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i> and <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> (lievito madre), herbs and spices, cooked and sliced. It is currently sold in slices resembling animal salami (bresaola veg, salami veg, etc.). The market is considered mature for the introduction of new food preparations that are not presented anymore as salami-like products.</p> <p>The objective of the challenge is to identify new food preparations and marketing messages to address the consumers.</p> <p>Background knowledge: production technology of Mopur, legislation, food logistics, marketing, communication.</p> <p>Abilities: understanding food production (food production, consumption, market), identifying solutions to a problem by considering various point of view and possible actions, work in a team, prototyping solutions, preparing</p> <p>The challenge is composed by online meetings and face-to-face activities. In addition, a visit to a production plant (Felsineo veg) is foreseen.</p> <p>The challenge is divided in the following steps with the related methodology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Launch of the challenge (meeting with the challenge provider – Felsineo veg) ● Background acquisition (production technologies, packaging, communication and marketing, etc.) ● Brainstorming ● Identification of solutions and refinement ● Prototyping the solution ● Testing with end-users and final refinement ● Preparation of the pitch and showcase of the solution. ● Preparation and submission of the feasibility report
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	<p>Books: Meat and Meat Replacements, An Interdisciplinary Assessment of Current Status and Future Directions</p> <p>Papers: Meat substitutes: current status, potential benefits, and remaining challenges, Opportunities for the Adoption of Health-Based Sustainable Dietary Patterns: A Review on Consumer Research of Meat Substitutes</p> <p>Websites: https://shop.felsineoveg.com/mopur/</p>
Notes	
Description of eventual requirements	The challenge is suitable for students with background in information technology, engineering, food technologies, socio-economics, psychology, biology, agricultural sciences

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #3	
Reference Person	Gian Luca Foresti, Pier Luca Montessoro, Luca Di Gaspero
Key-descriptors	
Title	Self-assessment tools for ICT courses
TAGS	
Date	October 2023 – September 2025
Participants	
Details	
Description of event and programme	This project involves the development of various self-assessment tools as part of courses in the ICT sector such as: Fundamentals of Computer Programming, Data Structures and Algorithms, Logical Networks, Computer Architecture, Operating Systems, Computer Networks.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	https://elearning.uniud.it/moodle/login/index.php (please send an email to pierluca.montessoro@uniud.it for a guest account)
Notes	
	Activity continuing from Milestone #27

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #3	
Reference Person	Gian Luca Foresti, Francesca Zanon
Key-descriptors	
Title	Video Analysis and Teacher Training
TAGS	
Date	October 2023 – September 2025
Participants	
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>In line with the developments in teacher training approaches, the most recent literature emphasizes the potential of video analysis in promoting the professional vision of teachers. In particular, by offering the opportunity for a “second-hand” experience of teaching through the immersion in authentic classroom situations captured in their richness and complexity, video analysis can foster the development of noticing and reasoning skills supported by a process of recursive interaction between theory and practice.</p> <p>The project pursues the following aims:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Develop a system of methodologies, tools and procedures for video analysis to foster the improvement of the teaching skills of university teachers - Test the system within a pilot training course aimed at UniUD teachers
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	https://elearning.uniud.it/moodle/login/index.php (please send an email to pierluca.montessoro@uniud.it for a guest account)
Notes	
	Activity continuing from Milestone #27

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #3	
Reference Person	Gian Luca Foresti, Luca Casarsa
Key-descriptors	
Title	E-Racing Team
TAGS	Formula Student, Electric car, Formula Electric
Date	October 2023 – September 2025
Participants	
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The project is open to students from the second year onwards of the courses of study offered at the University of Udine (not limited to engineering studies).</p> <p>The aims of the project is to provide to the participating student the opportunity to develop a complete engineering project, with the final purpose to design, produce and test an electric competition vehicle to participate to the Formula Students championship.</p> <p>The University of Udine has participated for the first time in 2023 to the Formula Student events held in Italy and Spain. The project will continue the next years with the development of the existing vehicle and with new students involved in the team. By their participation to the projects, the students have the opportunities to empowering their engineering skills and acquire new soft skill that will be surely useful for a faster and smoother entry into their professional life</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	https://www.formula-ata.it/ https://www.formulastudent.es/
Notes	
	Activity continuing from Milestone #27

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #3	
Reference Person	Gian Luca Foresti, Luca Casarsa
Key-descriptors	
Title	AeroUD
TAGS	Air Cargo Challenge
Date	October 2023 – September 2025
Participants	
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The project is open to students from the second year onwards of the courses of study on mechanical, electrical and managerial engineering.</p> <p>The aims of the project is to provide to the participating student the opportunity to develop a complete engineering project, with the final purpose to design, produce and test o fixed wing drone to participate at the international competition Air Cargo Challenge (ACC)</p> <p>The University of Udine has participated to ACC since 2015 and the team is currently working for the 2024 competition. The ACC is held every second year and organized by the winning team of the previous edition. It sees involved about 40 teams representing universities form all over the Europe, middle east and south Americas. By their participation to the projects, the students have the opportunities to empowering their engineering skills and acquire new soft skill that will be surely useful for a faster and smoother entry into their professional life</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	https://www.aachen-drone.de/acc-24/ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Air_Cargo_Challenge
Notes	
	Activity continuing from Milestone #27

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Franco Bonollo
Key-descriptors	
Title	The RAIDMAP experience: training students at design of R&I projects
TAGS	Horizon Europe, Research & Innovation, Technology Readiness Level
Date	June 2025, 1-day Workshop + remote team work + final workshop
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>RAIDMAP (RAw IDEas for MATERIALS Projects) is the result of an advanced Education initiative, supported by EIT – Raw Materials. The target is that of training “new” (engineering students) and “old” (professionals) generations at cooperating for the development of innovative ideas for future research projects in various Engineering fields.</p> <p>Students involved in RAIDMAP Project develop the following competencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the main issues related to Raw Materials and to their main criticality issues (availability, supply risk, environmental footprint, etc); • Knowledge on the basic structure of a Research Project (structure, work organisation, business plan, budget, evaluation of impacts, etc); • Working in a multidisciplinary and international team with colleagues with different backgrounds and cultural heritage, and with industrial tutors, joined together to develop new “European” ideas in the field of Raw Materials; • Capability of presenting project idea and structure in an international competitive context <p>RAIDMAP brings together students and industry through real technological issues, and is based on</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Starting event (1-day), properly designed in order to match students’ fresh ideas with professionals’ experience, approaching existing industrial issues on themes such as circular economy, recyclability and substitution of critical raw materials; • Team work, in which students, remotely coached by professional tutors will develop a project idea, followed by on-line presentations and preliminary selection; <p>Final workshop, in which students will present the up-graded project ideas to a board of experts, to check their potential for becoming real research projects or startups in the frame iNEST Ecosystem</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The RAIDMAP Experience - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=J04RZnH_BS4 • https://www.ingegneria.unipd.it/progetti/progetto-raidmap
Notes	

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives

SPOKE #5		
Reference Person	Franco Bonollo	
Key-descriptors		
Title	Transitions Technologies	
TAGS		
Duration	30 CFU	
Details		
Description of event and programme	<p>Transitions Technologies is a new educational project developed by the School of Engineering that aims to address the multidimensional problems posed by the ecological transition and the digital transition in support of infrastructure. Innovative courses have been developed, integrated with existing master's degree programmes, that have been designed to promote two new interdisciplinary professional roles: the Green Technologies Expert and the Smart Infrastructures Expert.</p> <p>The aim is to train young engineers who are able to operate in a timely and reliable manner within a rapidly-evolving technological environment, through an interdisciplinary approach to problem solving and a systemic view in addition to specific disciplinary training.</p> <p>The Transitions Technologies Project addresses the training of engineering professionals who are able to address the multidimensional problems posed by the ecological transition (the Green Technologies Expert) and by the digital transition in support of infrastructure (the Smart Infrastructures Expert). These topics are of great strategic relevance, both within the framework of the Next Generation EU Programme and within the context of the measures envisaged by the National Recovery and Resilience Plan for transversal skills.</p> <p>The Transitions Technologies programme offers flexible, interdisciplinary courses designed to enrich and enhance curricular activities and to create new professional roles, which are strategically relevant in the changing world of work.</p> <p>The educational programme for the Green Technologies Expert or the Smart Infrastructures Expert is established and integrated in a Master's degree programme, for a total of 30 educational credits (of which at least 21 educational credits are acquired in "transversal" fields and not in the main fields of the specific Master's degree):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 18 or 15 curricular educational credits as part of the minimum 120 educational credits for a Master's degree • 12 or 15 educational credits acquired as extra-curricular credits, in addition to the 120 educational credits required for a Master's degree 	
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.	
Website/link	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.ingegneria.unipd.it/en/degree/transitions-technologies • https://www.ingegneria.unipd.it/en/degree/transitions-technologies/multimedia-materials 	
Notes		
Remark	Activity started in autumn 2023, and will end on autumn 2025. Full report will be provided at that time	

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Carlo Mariconda, Sergio Canazza
Key-descriptors	
Title	IA for innovative learning
TAGS	
Date	20 January 2025
Details	
Description of event and programme	The Challenge aims at stimulating students and teachers at understanding potential and criticalities of AI, in terms of “technological ethics” and “digital rights”, to evaluate real applications, advantages and limits, with the support of national and international experts. The seminar will also face the questions on how assessment and formative objectives might change as a consequence of generative AI. The event will comprise a contest about AI.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rebX86fAbro
Notes	
Remark	

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives

SPOKE #6

Reference Person | Alessandra Bucossi

CHALLENGE Key-descriptors

Title | **The Venice Craft and Couture Hackathon**

TAGS |

Duration | 4 days

Details

Description of event and programme | The Venice Craft and Couture Hackathon is an educational event that unites the traditions of Venetian craftsmanship with the innovation of a leading Italian fashion brand. Over the course of four days, participants will explore, create, and celebrate the convergence of culture, heritage, and contemporary fashion. Artisans, whose skills have been honed through generations, will unveil their trade secrets. Participants will witness these crafts in action, from the art of Murano glass blowing to the intricate craft of lacemaking and mask crafting. It's not just about technique; it's about understanding the cultural significance that these crafts hold in the heart of Venice. With newfound inspiration and insights, participants return to the hackathon venue, ready to embark on the real challenge. The fashion brand presents its specific objectives and challenges related to incorporating traditional Venetian craft techniques into their designs. In diverse teams formed the previous day, participants brainstorm, ideate, and begin crafting innovative solutions. Workshops and mentorship sessions are held to support these creative endeavours. Experts in both fashion and craft provide guidance to help teams refine their concepts and develop prototypes.

1. Creative Brainstorming: Collaborative idea generation sessions.
2. Hands-On Workshops: Craftsmen lead skill-building workshops / Participants gain practical knowledge for their designs.
3. Mentorship and Expert Guidance: One-on-one and group mentoring from fashion and craft experts.
4. Prototype Development: Teams create and refine prototypes.
5. Judging and Awards: Judges evaluate projects for innovation and sustainability.
6. Networking and Collaboration: Opportunities for networking and future collaborations to promote ongoing innovation in fashion and craftsmanship.

Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST | The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.

Website/link |

Notes

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #6	
Reference Person	
CHALLENGE Key-descriptors	
Title	Sustainable Innovation Hackathon: Transforming the Motorship Concordia
TAGS	
Duration	4 days
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>Rising sea levels, the weight of tourism, and environmental concerns threaten the fragile equilibrium of Venice. Amidst these challenges, a unique opportunity has arisen. The Board of Directors of Actv, the public transportation company, has chosen not to dismantle the motorship Concordia. They see the potential for a sustainable future. The spotlight now turns to a group of university students with a shared passion for innovation and sustainability. Their challenge is to reimagine the motorship Concordia as a floating open laboratory and a symbol of sustainable development for Venice and its cherished lagoon. Stepping aboard the Concordia, participants will find themselves in the company of diverse minds, all driven by a shared purpose: to breathe new life into this iconic vessel and make it a beacon of sustainability and innovation. Teams will form, each dedicated to exploring the boundless possibilities. Envision harnessing cutting-edge technologies, embracing renewable energy sources, and choosing eco-friendly materials to transform the Concordia into an example of sustainable living. The lagoon itself becomes a canvas for creativity, a source of inspiration for ideas that not only rejuvenate the Concordia but also safeguard the fragile ecosystem of Venice's lagoon. Ideas will take shape through immersive workshops and enlightening presentations by experts in sustainability, marine engineering, and environmental conservation. These experiences will equip participants with the knowledge and inspiration needed to craft visionary solutions. The climax of this transformative event is the moment to shine—a presentation before a panel of judges, including industry experts, environmentalists, and visionaries. With passion and innovation, participants will pitch their visions for the Concordia's sustainable future, competing for prizes and, more significantly, the opportunity to leave an indelible mark on Venice and its lagoon.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design Thinking: User-centric problem-solving. • Collaborative Teams: Diverse groups for holistic solutions. • Sustainability Assessment: Evaluate environmental, social, and economic impacts. • Prototyping: Rapid development and refinement of ideas. • Expert Workshops: Insights from sustainability experts. • Pitch Development: Craft compelling project narratives. • Cross-disciplinary Learning: Knowledge sharing among participants. • Sustainability Metrics: Establish measurable project sustainability. • Environmental Impact Assessment: Evaluate ecological effects. <p>Community Engagement: Involve local stakeholders.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #9	
Reference Persons	Andrea Cangiani, Pasquale Africa, Gianluigi Rozza
Key-descriptors	
Title	School on digital twins for the human body
TAGS	digital twin deployment, high-fidelity modelling, biological organs modelling and simulation, model complexity, scalability, software engineering, HPC
Date	Fall 2025
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>High-fidelity modelling is core to digital twin deployments when accuracy, precision, and in-depth analysis are critical. However, it poses great challenges starting from model complexity and issues related to computational resources, data handling, real-time requirements, scalability and maintenance. This is particularly so when dealing with the high complexity inherent in the modelling of human organs, from the circulatory system to the brain, from the lungs to the single cellular system. The school aims at bringing together expertise on both modelling and high-fidelity numerical simulation of such human organs, providing insight knowledge of scientific computing software for the deployment of complexity reduction methods.</p> <p>This school aimed to research students, early career researchers and practitioners interested in the deployment of high-fidelity digital twins of human organs.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE 9	
Reference Persons	Andrea Cangiani, Rene' Butto
Key-descriptors	
Title	PhD for Innovation
TAGS	Problem solving
Date	2 days workshop + 3 months challenge, in 2025
Details	
Description of event and programme	PhD for innovation is an initiative of SISSA aimed at PhDs willing to work for a short time on a problem of innovation posed by one of our industrial partners. Students learn soft skills such as time management, the ability to work in groups and to communicate their results to the stakeholders. At the same time, the challenge gives industries and institutions working in research & development the opportunity to innovate by acquiring access to state-of-the-art techniques.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	https://valorisation.sissa.it/phd-innovation
Criteria for Certification	
Evaluation methods	Presentation of results, evaluation from stakeholders

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Innovation Ecosystem

Cross-Cutting Activity #4

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Annex 6

***Lifelong
Learning
Courses***

***Scheduled
for
Milestone #28***

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #1	
Reference Person	Daniele Morselli
Key-descriptors	
Title	Challenge based learning: the pedagogy to develop 21st century skills
TAGS	Pedagogy, innovation, challenge, self-directed learning, problem-based learning, 21 st century skills
Date	
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The participants will learn how to design and deliver a complete cycle (or module) of challenge-based learning, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Selection of the challenge and wording - Making the groups of students and techniques for effective groupwork (for example the jigsaw, cooperative learning, etc..) - Timeline with selection of activities to find a solution to the challenge (for example: the problem solving process, ideation, pitching, presenting, the business model canvas, Design thinking techniques, making web searches, etc...); - Use of digital technologies to favor collaboration (shared files, Google Jamboards) - Coaching techniques; - Set the reflection and self-assessment tasks for learning from experience. <p>The competences generally developed in students through challenge-based learning are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - finding an evidence-based solution to a community impacting challenge (problem solving); - working in groups on a challenge (teamwork); - making web searches and find evidence to back a solution (find evidence-based solutions); - pitching/presenting a solution to an authentic audience.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #1	
Reference Person	Margherita Molinaro
Key-descriptors	
Title	Sustainable supply chain management in mountain areas
TAGS	Supply chain management, Sustainability, Mountain areas
Date	
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>During the lectures and seminars, the participants will acquire an integrated and strategic knowledge of sustainable supply chain management, developing solid managerial skills on how to deal with the main peculiarities and criticalities that characterize the mountain areas. Upon course completion, besides developing an advanced understanding of sustainability and supply chain management concepts, the participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - recognize and evaluate the risks and criticalities that can affect the supply chains located in mountain areas; - evaluate and adopt tools and approaches for sustainable purchasing in mountain areas; - evaluate pros and cons of possible innovative solutions for sustainable logistics in mountain areas; - understand the importance and advantages of sustainability certifications; - conceptually design solutions and approaches for circular economy in mountain areas - understand the principles of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), including the potential and limitations of the method.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #1	
Reference Persons	Fabrizio Mazzetto, Andreas Mandler
Key-descriptors	
Title	Introduction to Smart Agriculture Technologies for Mountain Ecosystems
TAGS	Smart Agriculture, Life-Long Learning, Farm Management Information System
Credits	3 ECTS
Date	
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>This introductory course – offered within the life-long learning program of the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano <i>Studium Generale</i> – invites interested people to enter to the world of Smart Agriculture (SA) with a special focus on Mountain Innovation Ecosystems. The general definition refers to interconnected and automated technologies to be applied at agri-environmental enterprises (farms, forestry, livestock farming systems) to enable advanced forms of data-driven management decisions.</p> <p>The course will give a general understanding of the SA domain by presenting central concepts, definitions and technologies. Practical applications and needs will even regard mountain contexts, with a focus on extensive farming systems and the needs to identify new full production chains based on niche crops to be entirely carried at mountain farms. Lectures will start with background knowledge on farm mechanization, as well as technologic, economic and site-specific requirements. Common and well-known smart farming applications in crop production, livestock farming, fruit production and agro-forestry will be presented and discussed.</p> <p>Further on, basic components of every SA system will be considered more in detail, with a focus on the following components: sensors, identification systems, positioning systems (GNSS), actuators, hardware and software elements enabling advance decisional application at the enterprises. The way by which all the components will be integrated into a Farm Information Systems (FIS)/ Farm Management Information System (FMIS) will be finally discussed, together with the “decision-oriented” approach (=infologic) to be adopted when designing a new FIS/FMIS.</p> <p>The practical part of the course will focus in detail on the use of the above components (e.g., positioning systems to map entities and land shapes; GIS for managing digital maps importing specific field data; computation strategies for geo-data interpretation to be used in farm management decisions).</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	https://www.unibz.it/it/faculties/further-courses/studium-generale/
Notes	

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE 1	
Reference Person	Monica Parricchi
Key-descriptors	
Title	Financial education for university students and graduates: build life skills
TAGS	Money, financial education, awareness, future, mountain economic
Date	
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>Financial literacy combines personal finance, financial concepts, and financial planning to help individuals build wealth and establish long-term stability. Financial literacy is crucial for young adults as they embark on life events involving major expenditure and debt, particularly for university students who are making labour market decisions.</p> <p>Objective: To provide students with comprehensive financial education skills to make informed financial decisions, manage their finances effectively, and plan for their future financial well-being. There will be a series of workshops covering key financial topics. By the end of the module, students should be well-prepared to manage their finances effectively and achieve their financial goals. The course will be organized into 20 hours of blended learning teaching, in presence and synchronous online.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #1	
Reference Person	Daniele Morselli
Key-descriptors	
Title	Curriculum design for university and secondary school's instructors
TAGS	Pedagogy, course design, competence-based education; learning outcomes; assessment, teaching and learning activities.
Date	
Details	
Description of event and programme	Upon completion of the course, the participants will learn how to design a module or course constructively aligned, that is with coherent intended learning outcomes, teaching and learning activities and assessment tasks. The participants will also learn to use the most common digital tools to improve engagement and participation (Mentimeter, Padlet, Socrative) as well as cooperation through shared files (Jamboards, Excel, Word). Participants will eventually reflect in written form on the difference between deep and surface learning and how to promote deep learning, thus developing their own scholarship of teaching.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #1	
Reference Person	Daniele Morselli, with partner Universities
Key-descriptors	
Title	Experimental procedure to certify transversal skills to facilitate the transition university to work
TAGS	Competence development, employability skills, sustainability, entrepreneurship, validation, certification, assessment
Date	
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>Certification of competence will be made through assessment or validation.</p> <p>Tools for competence assessment through a problem-solving situation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ an authentic situation, realistic task, simulation according to the selected vocation (this could span for example from 2 to 4 hours to allow for the student's competences expression); ○ During the problem-solving situation above, through specific leading questions, written self-reflection on the situations where the competence has been expressed (to assess how they signify the competence); ○ Interviews or focus groups with the learners on the problem-solving situation and on what the students have learnt (searching for their learning outcomes). <p>Tools for competence validation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Analysis of student's portfolio, also to make emerge the competences develop in non-formal and informal contexts (outside school-university) in lifelong learning perspective; ○ interview on portfolio and on the problem-solving situations where the competence has been developed. <p>How competence assessment works: for each experimental path (for example with 25 learners), only a selected number of competences (e.g. 6 to 10) will be certified. The certification is made through the 8 levels of the European Qualification Framework, these describes professional qualifications in terms of knowledge, skills and competences along 8 levels spanning from the upper secondary school (level 4 is school diploma) to second degree (level 6) and doctorate (level 8). When a competence is underdeveloped (example level 2), this is not simply certified.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #1	
Reference Person	Daniele Morselli & Michele Cagol
Key-descriptors	
Title	UP2: The Pedagogies to develop XXIst Century Skills
TAGS	#Pedagogy, #innovation, #self-directedlearning, #problem-basedlearning, #21stcenturyskills, #ArtificialIntelligence
Date	
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The course is for university instructors (researchers & professors) willing to improve their teaching methods. There are no further entry requirements.</p> <p>The module features online meetings (two hours' long) on weekly basis on specific aspects of teaching and learning in modern universities, which includes the use of Artificial Intelligence in university contexts for teaching and learning. The overall length of the course is 30 hours.</p> <p>Upon participating actively in the course, participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand specific pedagogies and AI - Apply these pedagogies and use of AI to their teaching - Reflect and improve on own scholarship of teaching and learning <p>A survey will be sent out to determine the participants' teaching needs.</p> <p>Planned contents:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The pedagogies of Challenge and Problem Based learning; - Teaching and learning in a multilingual environment; - Microteaching to improve teaching skills; - The use of Learning Management System to improve student's learning; - The use of AI for teaching and learning. - The theory of constructive alignment to promote deep learning; - Assessment strategies in the Universities of the XXIst century - Universal Design for Learning <p>The course will be delivered online through Teams. It will be student-centred and interactive with short lectures and group activities in the breakout rooms. The use of digital tools such as Socrative, Mentimeter, Padlet as well as a Learning Management System will promote active participation. To foster participation the lessons will be offered once a week, and in late afternoon time. Each lesson will deal with a specific topic so that miss a lesson will not constitute a problem to continue the course. Lessons will be recorded and therefore available for later use.</p> <p>A certificate of participation will be given to the participants who will take part in at least 80% of the meetings.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #2	
Reference Person	Federico Schena
Key-descriptors	
Title	Facilitate digital integration in healthcare.
TAGS	Extract keywords from the project. Innovation, Change, Digitization, Social and health services, Territorial services, Primary care, Lifestyles, Healthcare/social healthcare professionals
Date	Second semester 2025
Participants	
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>Summer School for facilitators of integrating digital solutions is divided into two contexts: a) in the clinical care practice of local health and social services and b) in promoting healthy lifestyles.</p> <p>The courses will be divided into five days for 40 hours and in 4 training modules partly shared (modules 1 and 3) between different groups of professionals and partially addressed to specific areas.</p> <p>Module 1 - Technological dynamics in the current healthcare and organizational and digital innovation scenario</p> <p>Module 2a - Co-design of clinical-care processes that can be improved and redesigned with digital solutions also about economic sustainability.</p> <p>Module 3 - Change management models and tools</p> <p>Module 4a - Digital literacy of citizens and patients</p> <p>Module 2b – the promotion of lifestyles and healthy choices</p> <p>Module 4b – Use of digital tools to encourage and monitor the adoption of active health behaviors.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	
Description of eventual requirements	<p>The training project aims to encourage acquiring skills to maximize the adoption of digital solutions within clinical care practice to accompany the reorganization and reorientation processes of local health and social services.</p> <p>The training activities will take place in a residential summer school and include interactive teaching activities, workshops, and group work supervised by expert teachers.</p>

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #2	
Reference Person	Carlo Casonato
Key-descriptors	
Title	Digital transition, health and well-being between ethics and technology for sustainable and citizen-friendly innovation
TAGS	Innovation, social innovation, multidimensional evaluation, law, ethics, HTA, value
Date	Scheduled 1st semester 2025
Participants	
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The tremendous technological, social, and climatic transformations are having and will have an ever more significant impact on society. Managing these phenomena requires updated, adequate, and transversal skills concerning the different social actors (individual, community, business, and decision-maker). A paradigmatic case is the digital transition and its decline to benefit the citizens' health and well-being. Technological innovation is expected to improve the system's capabilities to respond to growing health needs. However, it raises new questions about the accuracy of the cost-benefit ratio and its ethical and legal implications. These issues must become the heritage of professionals (decision-makers, users, and developers) and end users (patients and citizens). The objective of this intervention is to develop multilevel literacy on the topic of the digital transition as an enabling tool for the development of good health.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Five Seminars open to the population and decision-makers on the topics of Digital transition, health needs, and social impact..; - Ten lessons (10) open to university students with a technological, humanistic, or legal background on the topic of: Value of technological innovation in healthcare and its ethical, legal, and social implications. - Workshop for doctoral students and young researchers on AI in Medicine, state of the art, health expectations, ethics, law
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	
Description of eventual requirements	Multiple targets differentiated by the type of intervention: Citizens and decision-makers, Master's degree students, Ph.D. students, young researchers, and healthcare professionals

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #2	
Reference Persons	Giandomenico Nollo, Michele Nicoletti
Key-descriptors	
Title	Converging Frontiers: AI, Healthcare, Ethics, and Law
TAGS	Healthcare, Trustworthy and Human-Centered AI, Law and AI act, Ethics
Date	To be defined
Participants	
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The course is aimed at health professionals and gives them the tools to use the various AI systems with awareness and responsibility in prevention, diagnostics, treatment, and monitoring. In this way, the course aims to guide professionals in grasping all of AI's potential and managing and minimizing its risks.</p> <p>After a general introduction to the legal phenomenon and AI techniques, the course focuses on the ethical and legal principles that must inspire a medicine centered on the well-being of the patient and the promotion of their respective rights, starting from those linked to the care relationship. Particular attention is paid to the Artificial Intelligence Act, which will soon be approved at the European level.</p> <p>Depending on the hours available, the topics of data processing and privacy (GDPR) and liability (AI liability directive) may be added.</p> <p>Further editions of the course, of a more interdisciplinary nature, may simultaneously be aimed at health professionals and developers of AI systems.</p> <p>Law: introduction to the purposes and similarities of medicine</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AI: state of the art, definitions and typologies, applications - AI act: <p>Structure and risk-based approach,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Principles and requirements: transparency and explainability, Human oversight, robustness and safety, equality and fairness <p>Data processing, privacy (GDPR)</p> <p>Responsibility (AI liability directive)</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	
Description of eventual requirements	Degree in medicine and surgery Degree in nursing

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #4	
Reference Person	Denis Maragno
Key-descriptors	
Title	Spatial information system for spatial planning
TAGS	Gis, remote sensing, geodatabase, special planning
Duration	20 hours of a-synchronous on-line lessons
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The scientific content of the course is concerned with the study of theories and processes useful for effectively exploiting, creating, and disseminating geographical information in response to a spatial problem.</p> <p>The course teaches the knowledge and skills to manage data from new ICT technologies to support spatial, urban, and environmental planning processes. The course develops skills and competencies for using big data and Remote Sensing Analysis and evaluating specific analytical methods to extract value and knowledge from them.</p> <p>The urban issues studied will concern environmental sustainability and climate-proof planning. For the two fields of study, the course will focus on defining working processes capable of constituting an innovative and effective cognitive framework for the spatial assessment of the three fields, from which to implement planning solutions and support decision-making.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New information technologies for spatial planning; • Gis and Giscience; • General principles and tools for database management; • Geographic component in databases (DB) and differences between the cartography and geo-database paradigms; • Vector" and "raster" models; • Principles of modelling reality through spatial databases; • Remote Sensing Analysis and satellite data; <p>Techniques and tools to produce thematic maps;</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	
Availability of the Course	We have been carrying out two activities related to online courses. On one hand, we initiated the recording of courses, thereby launching an experimental approach to teaching. This also involved developing comprehensive guidelines to support instructors in independently recording their video lectures. On the other hand, we established a new agreement between Iuav and EduNOVA, which coordinates the EduOpen platform where the MOOCs will be hosted. This collaboration aims to streamline the integration of our courses into the platform and extend the overall learning experience for participants. The course described above is almost fully recorded and will be published on the EduOpen platform in December 2024.

Image of the Course	
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Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #4	
Reference Person	Tiziano Dalla Mora
Key-descriptors	
Title	Lighting Design and Assessment
TAGS	Indoor light, lighting parameters, lighting tool and software
Duration	20 hours of a-synchronous on-line lessons
Details	
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>The objective is to understand the many aspects involved in the arrangement of lighting environments and to make informed choices, also considering the different characteristics of the available sources.</p> <p>Starting with the nature and definition of light, the mechanism of vision will be studied, analyzing the response of the visual system to different stresses. Photometric quantities and qualities will be reviewed to describe both light sources and illuminated surfaces.</p> <p>There will be no shortage of aspects involving light sources, natural light and luminaires, in particular LEDs technology.</p> <p>The last notions will have a more applied slant: calculation techniques and criteria for the design of indoor and outdoor lighting will be addressed, considering aspects related to performance and visual comfort and those related to energy saving.</p>
Contents of the course	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● FUNDAMENTALS OF LIGHTING <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature of light. Human eye and light perception, visual and non-visual effects. ● PHOTOMETRIC QUANTITIES <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Luminous efficiency. Luminous flux. Illuminance. Luminance. ● PHOTOMETRIC QUALITIES <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Elements of colorimetry. The color of objects. Color and architecture. Color temperature. ● CERTIFICATIONS AND STANDARDS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Lighting comfort. Veiling, Disability glare, luminance balance. ○ Standards and requirements (EU/Italian regulations). ○ Energy-saving and domotics in lighting. LENI index. ● LIGHTING LAMPS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Indoor and outdoor lighting sources and lamps. ○ LEDS. The color perception and power supply of LEDS. ● INTERIOR ARCHITECTURAL LIGHTING <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Computational and simulation methods and software as a design tool. ○ Indoor lighting strategies against glare. ○ Lighting for commerce and domestic use.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	

Availability of the Course	We have been carrying out two activities related to online courses. On one hand, we initiated the recording of courses, thereby launching an experimental approach to teaching. This also involved developing comprehensive guidelines to support instructors in independently recording their video lectures. On the other hand, we established a new agreement between luav and EduNOVA, which coordinates the EduOpen platform where the MOOCs will be hosted. This collaboration aims to streamline the integration of our courses into the platform and extend the overall learning experience for participants. The course recording is in progress and will be published on the EduOpen platform in January 2025.
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Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #4	
Reference Person	Massimiliano Condotta
Key-descriptors	
Title	Applied architectural acoustics
TAGS	Room Acoustic - Reverberation Objective acoustic parameters - Open-source acoustic simulation software
Duration	20 hours of a-synchronous on-line lessons
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Basic knowledge of Mathematics, Physics and 3D cad modelling
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>The course will start from the fundamentals of acoustic: the concept of sound and the physical quantities that characterize it will be defined. The theoretical basis will be provided to understand the methods of sound propagation in free fields and in closed environments. Sound-absorbing materials and objects and their application will be described, analyzing manufacturers' technical data sheets.</p> <p>The concepts of reverberation (EDT RT20 RT30) and other objective acoustic parameters (C50 C80 Sti) useful for defining the acoustic characteristics of an environment will be defined.</p> <p>Finally, examples will be carried out in the classroom using open-source acoustic analysis software, applying the theoretical concepts learned.</p>
Contents of the course	<p>List of topics (indicatively, one topic/sub-topic, for each scheduled lecture)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fundamentals of acoustics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ sound and acoustics ○ acoustic quantities ○ Sound signal analysis ○ psychoacoustic • Room acoustic <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ image source method ○ indoor sound-field ○ reverberation time ○ sound absorption ○ Objective acoustic parameters • Case studies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ in situ acoustic measurements ○ calculation of the acoustic characteristics of closed environments using analytical methods • calculation of the acoustic characteristics of closed environments using analytical methods <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ description of the calculation software ○ classroom calculation examples • classroom calculation examples

Teaching Methodologies	On-line a-synchronous lectures
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spagnolo R. Acustica. Fondamenti e applicazioni 2015 Utet • Everest F. A. Manuale di acustica. Concetti fondamentali, acustica degli interni 1996 Hoepli – Milano • Egan. D. Architectural Acoustic – 2007 J Ross Pub • Ermann M. Architectural Acoustics Illustrated – 2015 John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken, New Jersey. • I-Simpa - An Open Source software for 3D sound propagation modelling https://i-simpa.univ-gustave-eiffel.fr/
Notes	

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #4	
Reference Person	Isabella Friso, Giulia Lazzaretto
Key-descriptors	
Title	Elementi base di disegno digitale
TAGS	Architectural representation, drawing software, technical drawing 2d and 3d, advanced graphic tools
Duration	30 modules of variable length
Details	
Preliminary requirements	None
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	This course provides an introduction to architectural representation techniques, focusing on the use of various drawing software. It covers both 2D and 3D technical drawing, including fundamental skills in AutoCAD and Rhinoceros, as well as advanced graphic tools in Photoshop and InDesign for creating detailed architectural visuals. Participants will learn how to navigate and utilize key features of these programs, mastering the essential tools for precise and professional architectural design.
Contents of the course	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Module 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Representing ○ Drawing ○ Orthogonal projections (plans, elevations, sections) ○ Raster / Vector • Module 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Software for architecture • Module 3 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Software for post production and graphics
Teaching Methodologies	On-line a-synchronous lectures published on Eduopen platform
References	
Notes	
Evaluation Methods	Evaluation of an individual exercise on a case study performed by the student
Notes	Using this course as the first example, the goal is to use EduOpen as a collection platform for the MOOC courses that have already been developed by instructors in the past, in order to systematize the production and collection of this type of content in a single repository.

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Franco Bonollo
Key-descriptors	
Title	Sustainability & Standards
TAGS	EU Standards, CEN, UNI
Duration and date	24 hours, second semester 2025
Details	
Description of event and programme	
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	
Remark	Programme is still in discussion with UNI, Italian Standard Organization

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Eleonora Di Maria
Key-descriptors	
Title	Training Modules on LCA & Life Cycle Thinking
TAGS	Life cycle assessment, Life Cycle Thinking, sustainability assessment, circular economy
Duration and date	24 hours, a-synchronous online Course, available from spring 2025
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The module is organized into 5 sections:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. introduction to LCT and LCA; 2. LCA principles and framework; 3. LCA to support environmental labels; 4. Life Cycle approach for sustainability assessment; 5. LCA for circular economy and for energy transition. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to LCT and LCA: Introduction to Life Cycle Thinking (LCT) and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA); History of LCA and LCT; Need and benefits of an LCT approach for companies; Need and benefits of an LCT approach for the market; Need and benefits of an LCT approach for the public sector; Definition and approaches to sustainability; Examples: 17 Sustainable Development Goals, three pillars of sustainability; European policies related to Sustainability. • LCA principles and framework: ISO standards for LCA: ISO 14040 and ISO 14044; Goal & scope of LCA; Life cycle Inventory and Life Cycle Impact Assessment; Interpretation of results and Critical Review process; Strengths and weaknesses/advantages and disadvantages/ limitations of LCA; • LCA to support Environmental Labels; Carbon footprint (climate change) and Water Footprint (water scarcity); Ecological footprint (land use) and Ecological backpack / backpack (resource consumption); EPD and PEF. • Life Cycle approach for sustainability assessment: Social LCA (S-LCA); Life Cycle Costing (LCC); Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA); Examples of S-LCA, LCC, SLCA • LCA for circular economy and for energy transition: LCA to compare recycling options; LCA to support circular innovation; LCA in renewable energies; LCA to support technology innovation and CE
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Franco Bonollo, Paolo Ferro
Key-descriptors	
Title	Training Modules on Eco-sustainable Design
TAGS	Eco-design, Circular Economy Design, European sustainable product initiative
Duration and date	24 hours, a-synchronous online Course, available from spring 2025
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The module introduces to a system understanding of Eco-sustainable design, the concept of a Circular Economy and Design requirements from a systemic perspective as well as a material related design. At the end of the course, the participants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • understand the Circular design concepts, design strategies and how to apply them to individual products; • have an understanding of strategies, methods and tools to implement Eco-sustainable Design; • can prioritize ways to improve the circularity of a product from a systemic life cycle perspective, including materials selection in a CRM scenario; • are aware of CRM related issues with material selection process; • are able to understand the limits of design intervention and indicate potential for the integration of Eco-design strategies in the organization strategy; • have knowledge of various different examples of specific cases. <p>Ecodesign and the Circular Economy – Ecodesign in the design process, what skills and focus when? – Ecodesign in EU-Regulation – Circular business models – Product/Service/System-Design - a new leverage for sustainability – A basic introduction to reliability in electronic systems – Energy related design aspects – Deep dive Electronics - Understanding impacts and design – Materials in design and related issues (CRM) – The design process: concept, embodiment, details – A materials selection systematic approach – Co-selection material and shape to serve for material use improved efficiency – How to face multi-objectives design problem in material selection – Eco-design driven material choice</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Silvia Gross
Key-descriptors	
Title	Training Modules on Critical Raw Materials
TAGS	Critical Raw Materials, Resources, Recycling, Urban Mining
Duration and date	24 hours, a-synchronous online Course, available from spring 2025
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The training module aims at introducing the topics of critical raw materials by contextualizing it into the broader framework of natural resources and their scarcity. The module will present the resource topic, along with its regulatory framework, and will then introduce the topic of critical and strategic raw materials along the whole value chain (mining, processing and use, recovery, recycling, End of Life/End of Waste, overall and supply chain). A particular focus will be on mitigation strategy to address criticality (i.e. substitution, recovery, urban mining). A focus on a selection of CRM will be made.</p> <p>Knowledge & abilities to be achieved: recognize and assess CRM and SRM, understanding their technological and economical relevance and the critical issues related to their supply and recovery. Acquire a basic knowledge of main recovery and recycling processes.</p> <p>Introduction to resources management – Introduction to Critical and Strategic Raw Materials – Critical Raw Materials act – Relevance of raw materials for strategic technologies – Supply chain of CRM – Mining of CRM and mining charts – Mitigation measures – Urban Mining – Case Study: Rare earth elements – Case study: Lithium – Case study: Copper – Further CRMs – Recovery of CRM: pyro, hydrometallurgical approaches and alternative approaches</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #6	
Reference Person	Fabrizio Panozzo
Key-descriptors	
Title	Mentoring creative enterprises in tourist destinations
TAGS	Mentorship, Creative Enterprises, Tourist Destinations, Social Innovation, Sustainability
Date	To be held in 2025
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>The module offers a transformative journey to craft-makers within the iNest ecosystem. The primary aim is to enrich their entrepreneurial acumen while nurturing their sense of social responsibility within the local community. This module is a blend of knowledge acquisition and skill development, focusing on key areas such as social innovation, sustainability, place branding, and tourism. Participants will delve into of craft enterprise fundamentals, from crafting business plans to mastering financial management and conducting market research, craft-makers will gain a solid foundation to thrive. The module will aslo explore the concept of social innovation and empower participants to identify opportunities for positive social impact within their community. They'll learn to envision their craft as a vehicle for meaningful change. Place branding is another facet of this module that will unlock participants' creativity. Participants will be able to craft compelling narratives and develop strategies to position themselves as cultural treasures within the iNest ecosystem. Tourism integration will expand craft-makers' horizons. Collaborating with tourism boards, they'll seamlessly blend their craft into the local tourism experience, expanding their reach and revenue streams. Community engagement will foster deep connections. Craft-makers will organize events, exhibitions, and cultural exchanges, forging bonds with local communities and nurturing a sense of belonging.</p> <p>The comprehensive module unfolds by covering essential craft entrepreneurship topics, emphasizing the creation of robust business plans and financial management. It then delves into social innovation, sustainability in craft production, and crafting unique place identities to position crafts as cultural treasures. The module explores the synergy between crafts and tourism, fostering collaborations with tourism boards, highlighting community engagement and developing soft skills. Real-world success stories inspire, and participants reflect on their impact and chart a path forward. The module concludes with graduation, preparing participants for ongoing mentorship and expanding their craft enterprises in the iNest ecosystem.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #6	
Reference Person	Fabrizio Panozzo
Lifelong learning Course Key-descriptors	
Title	Enhancing creative thinking with dance
TAGS	Choreography, Creative thinking, Dance skills, Improvisation, Communication
Date	To be held in 2025
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>This course is specifically designed for business managers, with a focus on enhancing their creative thinking skills. Participants will explore various dance skills, including gesture, improvisation, body awareness, and spatial thinking, all of which can be applied to the business context. Through the study of dance techniques, we'll emphasize the creative possibilities that arise from blending different physical practices. Dance is seen as a multidimensional art form, combining music, space, and relationships. We'll focus on the body's role in communication, interaction, and its ability to give abstract thoughts concrete form through improvisation techniques and theoretical concepts. This course offers business managers a unique journey to discover new meanings and interpretations while enhancing their creative thinking abilities.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Gesture and Expression in Business Communication 2. Improvisation Techniques for Creative Problem Solving 3. Body Awareness and its Impact on Leadership Presence 4. Spatial Thinking for Innovative Strategy Development 5. Creative Cross-Pollination Between Physical Practices 6. Multidimensional Artistry in Business 7. The Role of Music in Enhancing Business Dynamics 8. Leveraging Space and Environment for Business Success 9. Building Stronger Business Relationships through Movement 10. Concretizing Abstract Business Ideas through Improvisation
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #6	
Reference Person	Fabrizio Panozzo
Lifelong learning Course Key-descriptors	
Title	Enhancing creative thinking with contemporary art
TAGS	Art-Infused Leadership, Creative Problem-Solving, Emotional Intelligence, Interdisciplinary Learning, art-thinking
Date	To be held in 2025
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>This lifelong educational journey offers a comprehensive blend of creative thinking, critical analysis, and a heightened appreciation for the arts, empowering managers, and entrepreneurs to lead with innovation and inspiration throughout their careers. connections and seeing beyond the surface to unravel deeper meanings. Hands-on engagement with diverse artistic techniques, including drawing and painting, will provide participants with a unique platform to experiment with an inductive approach to thinking. This program immerses participants in the captivating world of artistic expression, where they will deeply understand the synergies between figurative and abstract representation. It empowers them to implement the art of reasoning through metaphors, allegories, and pre-logical mental connections, allowing for a level of strategic thinking that transcends the conventional boundaries of management. These insights provoke fresh perspectives, enriching their understanding of the world and enhancing their decision-making. Beyond knowledge acquisition, this program is a hands-on experience, fostering the development of tangible and invaluable abilities. Through practical engagement with various artistic techniques, participants will cultivate the skill of translating abstract concepts into concrete solutions. This immersive approach not only nurtures an innovative mindset but also equips individuals with the capacity to bring creative thinking to the forefront of problem-solving. The course comprises essential components such as foundational understanding of the art-leadership relationship, exploration of figurative and abstract art, creative problem-solving through artistic approaches, consideration of the emotional and aesthetic dimensions in decision-making, in-depth analysis of shared vocabulary between art and management, insights into the art appreciation experience and curatorial practices, practical application of artistic insights in leadership and entrepreneurship, opportunities for reflection and self-exploration, guest lectures from industry experts, a capstone project, community building and networking, and continuous learning resources.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #6	
Reference Person	Fabrizio Panozzo
Lifelong learning Course Key-descriptors	
Title	Enhancing creative thinking with theater
TAGS	Creative thinking, Theatre, Corporate context, Leadership
Date	To be held in 2025
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>This specialized module caters to business managers with a distinct focus on enhancing their creative thinking abilities by immersing them in the world of theatre, a compelling metaphor for the intricacies of corporate life. Throughout the program, participants will embark on a journey through various theatrical skills and concepts, including improvisation, storytelling, body language, spatial awareness, and public speaking, each of which holds profound relevance and applicability within the corporate context. By actively engaging in theatrical exercises and explorations, participants will gain profound insights and innovative strategies that seamlessly translate into the dynamics of the corporate world. These insights will span a broad spectrum of skills, encompassing effective communication, refined team dynamics, heightened adaptability, and innovative problem-solving approaches. This module aims to impart theoretical knowledge and facilitate hands-on experiences, allowing participants to integrate theatre principles into their professional repertoire. As they progress through the course, they will uncover how theatre techniques can serve as valuable tools to enhance leadership qualities, stimulate collaboration, invigorate creative thinking processes, and refine their public speaking acumen, all critical corporate attributes.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improvisation Skills 2. Business Storytelling 3. Non-Verbal Communication 4. Spatial Problem-Solving 5. Effective Public Speaking 6. Team Building through Theater 7. Creative Problem-Solving 8. Conflict Resolution Techniques 9. Empathetic Leadership 10. Adaptability and Change Management
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
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Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #7	
Reference Person	Elena Claire Ricci
Lifelong learning Course Key-descriptors	
Title	Sustainability and Agri-Food: awareness bites (20hx two editions)
TAGS	#sustainability #agri-food #entrepreneurship #EntreComp #Innovative Education
Date	March – September 2025
participants	Citizens; Students; Young (but not only) Entrepreneurs; Young (but not only) professionals
Details	
Description of event and programme	<p>Starting questions: How is it still possible to spread the culture of sustainability in the Agrifood sector? What do we need to improve? A) Technical skills (Agrifood), b) entrepreneurial skills; c) legal skills; d) communication skills.</p> <p>Most relevant topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical Skills. This module will build a deeper understanding of what is sustainability and sustainable development in general and in the context of the food system, and how business decisions can be analysed and compared from a sustainability perspective - An introduction to sustainability and how the concept of sustainable development can be applied in the agri-food domain. What are the dimensions of sustainability and how to measure impacts on such dimensions. Introduction on how to compare different choice options. - Entrepreneurship Competence: developing the attention to act upon opportunities and ideas, and to transform them into values for others; based on the abilities as creativity, critical thinking and problem solving, taking initiative and perseverance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The expected skills are based on diverse experience, cross-cultural competency, creativity, and managing diversity; the entrepreneurial competences leverage the networks and knowledge of trends in flexibility and agility - Legal Skills. Knowledge and skills: knowing that there is a European legal framework that is constantly evolving and which companies must take into account to operate in the market - Approval of two important directives: DIRECTIVE (EU) 2024/1760 of 13 June 2024, on corporate sustainability due diligence and amending Directive (EU) 2019/1937 and Regulation (EU) 2023/2859, nonché Directive 2024/825, of 28 February 2024, amending Directives 2005/29/EC and 2011/83/EU as regards empowering consumers for the green transition through better protection against unfair practices and through better information - Communication Skills. using tools offered by edutainment and science communication to spread their professional action in an effective and engaging but at the same time scientifically accurate way - The role of new media languages for science communication, also in connection with the entertainment dimension (e.g. TED Talks, theatrical performances on scientific dissemination, contents on YouTube, etc.).
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The event will be promoted through a targeted outreach strategy, including direct email invitations within the iNEST network and to relevant organizations or departments interested in the topic, and advertisement on social media channels.
Website/link	
Notes	

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #8	
Reference Person	Alberto Marinò, Donata Vianelli
Lifelong learning Course Key-descriptors	
Title	Digitalization and Sustainability in the Blue Economy
TAGS	Sustainability, Blue Economy, Energy, Ship & Marine technologies, Digital Twin, Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence
Duration and Date	35 hours – 1 week, Summer 2025
Participants	Engineering or Economics and Business or Informatics and Data Science Bachelor and Master students.
Details	
Description of event	The Summer School will focus on how sustainability and digitalization impact the industry involved in blue economy issues. The summer school program will cover problems, impacts, and opportunities that ports, shipyards, transport and logistic operators, and the maritime industry in general, face from the perspective of digitalization and sustainability. The teaching methodology will include frontal lessons, teamwork, and company visits.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The Summer School is open to max 30 students from all the iNEST Partners interested in deepening the digitalization and sustainability issues in the blue economy context.
Website/link	
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